

January 2025

**Cross-cutting activity 1:
Support to the generation and
the development of start-ups
and spin-offs**

**Leader:
Ca' Foscari University
of Venice**

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INTRODUCTION TO THE CROSS-CUTTING ACTIVITY 1 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES

This introduction provides a **comprehensive overview** of the progress of the Cross-cutting activity 1, starting from a **task completion** status summary table, then going task by task through the overall **results** and finally addressing the main **encountered problems, corrective actions** and **next steps**.

The introduction is followed by 9 reports, each offering a detailed perspective from one of the Spokes.

iNEST CC1 goal is to develop a feasible and functional framework, to support the generation and development of start-ups and spin-offs in the North-East of Italy ecosystem. The CC1 tasks (Pre-Acceleration, Acceleration, Fundraising) help academic and guiding research institutions interact among themselves and with the regional context, with the ultimate goal to contribute to regional development through continuous exchange and synergic on-the-field work. Therefore, within this picture, for the design implementation of an innovation ecosystem - functional for the generation and the development of research start-ups and spin-offs -, it is considered strategic to enable the development of these cross-cutting CC1 tasks, that deeply involve all Spokes.

A sum-up of iNEST CC1 **tasks status** as of January 2025 is provided in the following table:

Task	Leader	Sub-Task	Round1	Round2
Task CC1.1 Planning and validation	UniVE	Sub Task CC1.1.1: Planning of CC1 activities	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ongoing
		Sub Task CC1.1.2: Analysis of successful practices		
		Sub Task CC1.1.3: Data elaboration		
	IUAV	Sub Task CC1.1.4: Event and Communication	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Selection Day (Mar24) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Demo Day (Oct24) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OI Day (Jan25)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Selection Day (Dec25) <input type="checkbox"/> Demo Day (Jun25) <input type="checkbox"/> OI Day (TBD)
Task CC1.2 Pre- Acceleration	UniVE	Sub Task CC1.2.1: Engag. and training of the Key Actors	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
		Sub Task CC1.2.2: Implement. of the Scouting Stage		
		Sub Task CC1.2.3: Online Entrepreneurial training		
	UniUD	Sub Task CC1.2.4: Open innovation activities	OI Day: 30/01/2025	Jan25-Sept25
Task CC1.3 Acceleration	UniVR	Sub Task CC1.3.1: Dev. of the Key St. Elements	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
		Sub Task CC1.3.2: Engag. and coord. of the Key Actors	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
		Sub Task CC1.3.3: Implementation of the Acc. phase	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Jan25-Jun25
Task CC1.4 Fundraising	UniTS e PTAA	Sub Task CC1.4.1: Development of the Network	ongoing	
		Sub Task CC1.4.2: Implementation VC-Invested Stage		
	UniPD	Sub Task CC1.4.3: Design of the Sustainable Stage		

The tasks status can be described as follows:

- **CC1.1: Planning and validation:** planning for round 2 was completed in December 2024. Validation and periodical reviews are ongoing till the end of the project.
- **CC1.2: Pre-Acceleration:** completed 1st (Nov 2023 - March 2024) and 2nd (June - Dec 2024) Pre-Acceleration rounds. Completed research phase of the Open Innovation subTask, ongoing engagement of companies (1st Open Innovation Day: 30/01/2024).
- **CC1.3: Acceleration:** 1st Acceleration round implemented (April - October 2024), completed review and improvement of the Acceleration Framework for 2nd round; Key Actors engaged for both rounds; ongoing implementation of the 2nd Acceleration round (Jan - June 2025).
- **CC1.4: Fundraising:** the Task leader (UniTS, PAA) elaborated and proposed a work plan by August 2024 (including: short training on financing and contracts ABC; meetings with banks; "speed date" meetings with selected companies; external consulting for startup evaluation and 1:1 support in the path to fundraising and investor approaching). As of Jan. 2025 the implementation has not started, therefore the initiatives will be offered at the same time for startups of the 1st and 2nd Acceleration round. The design of initiatives for the "Sustainable stage" (leader: UniPD) is ongoing.

Concerning outputs, a comprehensive sum-up of overall **results** achieved as of January 2025 is:

within the **CC1.2 Pre-Acceleration task and subtasks**

- **Development of the Pre-Acceleration framework:** the previously designed scouting system of iNEST CC1 - providing a common strategy, a standard process and shared tools to the 9 Spokes, while enabling customised implementations according to each Spoke peculiarities - was further improved under guidance of the Program Leader and Scouting Officer. For the 2nd round a stronger focus was on targeted scouting efforts ("hunting"), addressing peculiar research groups. Guidelines for patent analysis and for researchers' funded projects analysis were developed. Key actors have access to an online repository where all the common documents, minutes and tools are progressively shared and stored.
- **Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (CC1.2.1):** after the initial engagement and training of the Scouting Specialists, and after the individual (almost weekly) coordination of the 1st round, all the Spokes have been continuously involved all together as a unique team during the 2nd round, with periodic monthly meetings (up to the Selection Day - December 3rd 2025) to discuss and review strategies, tools, activities progress, issues and results.
- **Implementation of the Scouting Stage to develop entrepreneurship from the universities' ecosystems and drive the research efforts towards a proof-of-concept (CC1.2.2):** for both rounds the engagement of the target groups proceeded in a decentralized way, with each Spoke collecting ideas from students, researchers and early stage startups (third mission and others linked to universities) using a custom approach, and in synergy with the internal initiatives led by Technology Transfer and IP Valorization. For the 2nd round the engagement mechanisms (events, calls for ideas, targeted meetings and communication activities) were reinforced with desk analyses of patents and funded projects within each University. Data collection tools and templates were further optimised and centralised (to ease post process data analysis). The funnel structure was maintained, as well as the evaluation criteria, but the contribution of an External Jury was added to the 2nd Selection Day evaluation procedure (60% weight on final score for CCI Committee, 40% weight for External Jury).

The **target n.** of applications to the Open Call was 100+ for each round (min 10 per Spoke) and the actual number of applications / ideas / early stage start-ups collected and their progression towards the Acceleration program was:

Pre-Acc. funnel stage	Round 1	Round 2
Open Call	179	173
Selection Form submission	66	70
CCI Committee evaluation	40	41
Selection Day	32	30
Admission into Acceleration	16	16

- Implementation of the basic online entrepreneurial training to provide a standardized model through the ecosystem (CC1.2.3):** open access international benchmarks of entrepreneurial education have been reviewed, after a selection, and then made available to the Spokes in a common shared online space. All the applicants have access to online entrepreneurial learning materials. The chosen benchmark for the learning objects is Stanford business school: <https://startupclass.samaltman.com>. Key themes of the online publicly available lessons are: how to get started, how to raise money, how to build products, and how to grow. Further custom learning objects to train the applicants on the preparation of a Pitch Deck were finalised in a step-by-step video guide released by the Program Leader, Prof. Carlo Bagnoli." A venture building documentation repository for further, deepening uses was set-up, too.

- **Open innovation activities (CC1.2.4):** the Open Innovation Manager performed a mapping and classification of innovation oriented companies in the North East, using a Pavitt set of indicators (defined with the support of the Program Leader and of Spoke 2 - UniTN) to select 66 innovative companies from Northeastern Italy. The 1st Open Innovation Day is scheduled on January 30th, 2025, in Padua, where the iNEST project will be presented and a symbolic recognition will be given to the 66 companies. The continuation will be the matching of the identified companies to the CC1 accelerated startups, taking into account the Macro themes.

within the CC1.3 Acceleration task and subtasks

- **Development of the Key Standardized Elements:** an Acceleration Framework was developed for the 1st round and with a learning-by-doing approach optimised for the 2nd round: a standardized “educational model” is provided through a centralised program based on itinerant workshops. The 2nd round framework, also based on the collected feedback, is characterised by a higher number of workshops (from 6 to 8) with reduced theory content and more practical work for building a solid strategic document (“strategic plan”) at the basis of the pitch. The software “Accelerator App” was implemented for more efficient work tracking, knowledge sharing, pace-keeping and reporting.
- **Engagement and coordination of the Key Actors:** the Acceleration management team was consolidated with the lead of UniTN (supported by HiT) and UniVR, and benefitted from the continuous contribution of the Scouting Officer, Assistant Scouting Officer and Communication team. Concerning the coaching system, the model was reinforced for the 2nd round, assigning to each startup 1 “expert/senior coach” bringing vertical expertise and 1 “operative coach” offering weekly 1h-meetings to better assist the cofounders throughout all the program. Based on competencies and commitment, some of the Scouting Specialists were also involved in the “operative coach” role. Throughout the entire duration of the 1st and 2nd Acceleration programs the management team met (and continues meeting) with regular weekly frequency. Coach coordination meetings are held monthly.
- **Implementation of the Acceleration phase:** the 1st round of the program was offered to 16 startups and completed by 11 of them. Towards the end of the 1st Acceleration program, some of the startups received a spontaneous interest from a number of different investors (such as: industrial, corporate and institutional funds and ventures, incubators, and even private equities). Therefore, 6 startups were guided by an Acceleration task force in the development of key documents to strengthen their preparedness for dialoguing with investors.

The 2nd round of the program is ongoing and is being offered to 15 startups; for this cycle an intermediate cut off was introduced to filter out of the program those teams that do not demonstrate sufficient commitment and that are not ready to complete the work required for a good performance at the Demo Day.

The contents of the workshops, for the 2 rounds, are reported in the following tables. For the 1st round a cycle of 5 webinars was also offered (Presentation of psychological types; Marketing, customer acquisition, sales; IP strategy; Data protection; Legal issues - Shareholders' agreements, term sheets, investment agreements) but revealed low interest and impact. Satisfaction surveys are periodically administered to the participant teams to assess and adapt the Acceleration program structure and features.

ROUND 1			
Date (2024)	Location	Sprint #	Workshop title
19-20 April	UNITS	1	Governance, Mission, Vision, Strategy and Business Model
			Problem and potential customer
10-11 May	UNIPD	2	Solution, value proposition and product POC
			Market, competitors and potential competitive positioning
31 May and 1 June	UniTN - Sol	3	Pitch session test
			Profit Model
5-6 July	SISSA	4	Operational model
			Economic-financial model
30-31 August	IUAV	5	Fundraising
			Company constitution and corporate governance
20 September	UNIVR	6	Pitch clinic
25 October	UNIVR	-	Demo Day

ROUND 2			
Date (2025)	Location	Sprint #	Workshop title
17-18 January	UNITN	1	Introduction and presentation of the strategic plan
7-8 February	UNIVR	2	Problem, actual solution and proposal
28 Feb and 1 March	UNIUD	3	Market and competition
14-15 March	UNIVE	4	Governance, mission & vision, strategy, business model; tools for AI
4 April	IUAV	5	Pitch clinic #1
cut-off			
9-10 May	UNIBZ	6	Action plan & Eco-Fin Plan
23-24 May	UNITS	7	Eco-Fin Plan & funding
6 June	UNIVR	8	Pitch clinic #2
cut-off			
(TBD) June	UNIPD	-	Demo Day

within the **CC1.4 Fundraising task and subtasks**

- **Development of the Fundraising Network and Management:** Spoke 8 (UniTS, PAA) members are currently involved in the call for experts and in the organisation of a series of events, according to their work plan.
- **Implementation of the VC-Invested Stage:** no results yet.
- **Design of the Sustainable Stage:** no results yet.

General outcomes from the cross cutting perspective are the good practices in dialogue settings among different Spokes, with the related common procedures and tools in Pre-Acceleration and Acceleration activities, that have been designed, implemented and fine-tuned.

Then, for the **encountered problems and (→) related corrective actions** in the cross cutting perspective, some reflections could be proposed:

- relatively low engagement of researchers in the 1st Pre-Acceleration round
 - starting from what emerged after the 1st Pre-Acceleration round, according to the progressive metabolisation of the updated regulatory framework (end of so called “professors privilege”) and leveraging on the PL’s orientation to the hunting/fishing tactic combination,, the result is a more targeted intervention with higher level of startup quality compared to the 1st round (also in the sense of BRL)
- 1st round divergences in SS modes of actions
 - intensified meetings of the SS team + regular ongoing reports (a report template was created and quite widely used, reducing dispersion and increasing uniformity and methodological convergence)
- end of Pre-acc. phase with Scouting Specialist contracts still active
 - integration between project phases as instructed by Program Manager and Program Leader (PL) (between Pre-acc. and Acc.)
 - redefinition of project roles in a logic of continuity: Scouting Specialists (SS) ideally accompany the startups along the Acceleration path as an operative coach (coach no longer a mentor) and/or assumes roles of connection between the last phase of the Acceleration and the Fundraising phase
 - engagement and skills development of SS aimed at consolidating the role in the territory even after the project end
- team vacancies → new tenders, onboarding and coordination actions
- high heterogeneity of the startups involved in the 1st Acc. round (in terms of background, themes, but also maturity) → characterisation of the portfolio (mix between TRL and BRL plausible for the market, for the success of the Acc. and subsequent phases or Fundraising)
- criticalities of the 1st Acc. program structure and outcomes
 - methodological curvature of the Acceleration framework, functional in giving more structure to the startups (equally enhancing the communication part - pitch - with the documentation part for each of the elements underlying a business plan/strategic plan, starting with the development from POC to MVP)
 - more hands-on way of conducting workshops (45min “lecture” + work with N coaches on the field)
 - more ws with introduction of an induced selection principle
 - implementation of software to support the Acc. phase, to give structure and continuity
 - intensification of coaching
- difficulties in defining criteria and indicators for the Open Innovation research action
 - collaboration of UniUD with UniTN, guided by the PL, successfully leading to the work methodology refinement and to the selection of a list of innovation oriented companies, divided into clusters
- delays in the implementation of the Fundraising phase → the Program Leader and Manager stimulated the Task leader towards the concretisation of the proposed work plan (combining the offer for the two “cohorts” of accelerated startups), while also outlining a backup action (based on networking) directly led by the CCI management team.

Next steps to be met in the cross-cutting perspective are:

- Open Innovation: awarding of companies at a public event at the University of Padua; contacting, visiting and selecting companies to intersect their open innovation issues with the inspiring development trajectories of startups.
- Fundraising: implementing the phase, offering tailored support + legal support, with coordinated action of Spoke 5 and Spoke 8.
- Integration between project phases on the instructions of Program Manager and Program Leader: between Acceleration and Fundraising.
- iNEST2: first meeting between iNEST Hub, Scouting Specialists, TTOs to strengthen the market exploitation of Technology Transfer.

References for the cross cutting perspective are in the common shared [Drive](#) environment, in the [CCI webpage](#) and inside the [Accelerator App CCI environment](#).

1. SPOKE 1 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1

Creating a startup is an exhilarating and daunting venture that requires thorough planning, strategic decision-making, and relentless determination. In today's fast-paced and highly competitive business landscape, it is crucial for aspiring entrepreneurs to engage in various activities that can pave the way for a successful startup. To achieve it, the Free University of Bolzano (unibz) has worked locally by extending his team with external personnel and implementing a call to find business ideas among his members; and at the consortium level by supporting the acceleration phase with various activities. Precisely, two experts on setting and developing start-up have been hired and worked on related tasks. Moreover, in February 2024 the university council has approved the first "[unibz call 4 startup](#)". The call had a lot of interest, 11 ideas were submitted, 4 of them were selected to follow the pre-acceleration phase. Finally, unibz has coordinated the participation of iNEST at [Bolzano slush'd](#) on September 3, 2024. Bolzano slush'd is a non-profit movement to promote innovation and entrepreneurial ambition among the most influential stakeholders in the local, national, and international ecosystem. Unibz has also planned a business challenge jointly with Loacker and Junior Enterprise Alto Adige, and a conference on the creation of innovative enterprises in order to promote iNEST and the CCI activities to unibz environment on September 2, 2024, see [program](#).

1.1. SPOKE "1" CCI OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW

Title: Ecosystems for mountain innovation

objectives and key results

The Free University of Bolzano leads the activities of the Spoke 1 "Ecosystems for mountain innovation" and develops research and technology transfer activities in the interdisciplinary area of mountain ecosystems. The main general objective is encouraging the development of new products, processes, and lifestyles capable of consolidating or supporting local traditions that guarantee the survival and demographic vitality of the mountain contexts from any standpoints (economic, environmental and social).

In the CCI activity, the first objective of unibz has been to create a team of scouting specialist and startup analysts. A scouting specialist acts as a strategic advisor, providing critical information and insights to guide decision-making for the startup. They help the startup to identify and capitalize on emerging opportunities, technologies, and partnerships that can contribute to its growth and success. The startup analyst plays a crucial role in providing financial insights, analysis, and recommendations to support the startup's growth and success. The team is composed by five professors and two external experts with specialization on scouting specialists, on ideation and market research to assessing funding options; producing business plans; and delivering new products to the market. The current goal is to enlarge further it.

The team has identified four possible ideas to present to iNEST selection. None of them has been selected for the acceleration phase.

The second objective of unibz has been to promote the pre-acceleration and acceleration phases. We planned an internal call for startups during spring 2024; and a business challenge jointly with Loacker and Junior Enterprise Alto Adige, and a conference on the creation of innovative enterprises in order to promote iNEST and the CCI activities to unibz environment on September 2, 2024. Moreover, unibz has coordinated the participation of iNEST at Bolzano slush'd on September 3, 2024, where three startups accelerated with the iNEST program were present.

1.2. SPOKE “1” CCI TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES

List of CCI Tasks:

- CC1.1: Planning and validation
- CC1.2: Pre-acceleration

The primary goal of this phase is to encourage university students, doctoral candidates, researchers, and pre-seed start-up members to participate in the Call for Exploring Ideas, where they have the opportunity to present potential ideas to transform into entrepreneurial projects.

To achieve this objective, 10 Scouting Specialists have been appointed, tasked with scouting potential entrepreneurs among students, researchers, and existing pre-seed start-up members. The scouting activity involves organizing individual meetings, where future entrepreneurs receive assistance in compiling a pitch deck. This is a crucial step in preparation for the Selection Day, the moment when the best ideas presented through the Call for Exploring Ideas will be selected to advance to the subsequent Acceleration phase. To encourage greater participation in the Call, each Spoke organizes promotional initiatives, such as events within universities or research institutes, where students and researchers are informed about the Cross-Cutting Activity.

- CC1.3: Acceleration

The Acceleration program consists of a series of workshops and webinars that combine theory and practice on innovation and entrepreneurship. In this way, teams receive all the skills and tools they need to make their start-ups successful. At the heart of the program is the so-called lean start-up methodology, which allows teams to rapidly test and modify their solution and market assumptions. This is a particularly effective approach for technologies emerging from research, which need a clear and flexible path to commercial exploitation.

Another essential component is peer learning, or mutual learning among participants. By sharing experiences, challenges, and solutions with others, teams can accelerate the development of their start-ups. Aspiring entrepreneurs also receive support from coaches—professionals from affiliated universities and institutes—who will help them put into practice what they have learned in the various workshops by adapting it to the context of their start-up.

The iNEST accelerator stands out for its ability to integrate different areas of innovation, from mountain and food innovation to advanced and sustainable manufacturing, tourism, and marine technologies. Supporting teams that deal with different technology sectors while respecting the different timeframes needed to validate the market is one of the biggest challenges iNEST will face.

- CC1.4: Fundraising

This is the management investment rounds, to get start-ups to enter the market and consequently scale up. This phase, just as the previous one, is managed in a centralized way, in order for start-ups to reach economies of scale using methodologies and technological platforms already developed and tested.

List of Spoke 1 RTs

- RTIA : Safety and quality of life in mountain Environments – Mountain Social Life

- RT1B: Safety and quality of life in mountain Environments – Mountain Habitat
- RT2: Resilience of Mountain production systems and supply chains
- RT3A: Decentralisation of Mountain Structures and Infrastructures – Energy Strategies
- RT3B: Decentralisation of Mountain Structures and Infrastructures – Logistic Strategies

Focus on Task CC1.2: Scouting and pre-acceleration activities in the Spoke 1

Background / State of the Art: the state of the art of the Free University of Bolzano cross activities component CC1 has been focused on team building, recruitment of personnel, promotion of activities, selection of potential start-ups and entrepreneurs.

Methodology: as mentioned above, through a call for applications we reached out to all academic staff at unibz to solicit their participation in the proposed support course in CC1 activities. We presented initial results in a conference on September 2 and coordinated with the consortium the participation to Bolzano slush'd.

Ongoing activities: unibz collaborates with iNEST to promote our activities and selected business ideas. The team will continue the collaboration with partners on the acceleration phase, including the participation to Bolzano slush'd. It is also working on further internal calls to identify project ideas and to promote further the technological transfer from university to the business world.

1.3. SPOKE "1" CC1 DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES

To disseminate its activities, the Free University of Bolzano has undertaken two primary initiatives. On September 2nd, the university organized a joint business challenge with Loacker and Junior Enterprise Alto Adige, along with a conference focused on fostering innovative enterprises.

In collaboration with the INEST consortium, the university coordinated INEST's participation in Bolzano Slush'd on September 3, 2024. Bolzano Slush'd is a non-profit movement promoting innovation and entrepreneurship among key stakeholders across the local, national, and international ecosystem. Three startups from the INEST Acceleration Program—Argo, rehub, and SINDREL—were selected to participate. These teams showcased their products at the INEST Consortium booth within the event's Exhibition Area, presenting to an audience of international investors, mentors, and business leaders. With over 800 attendees, Bolzano Slush'd provided an exclusive global platform for these three INEST-accelerated startups. Argo's technology aims to enhance the autonomy of visually impaired swimmers; rehub focuses on repurposing glass waste; and SINDREL has developed a device to simplify medication administration.

1.4. SPOKE "1" CC1 MAIN RESULTS

The Free University of Bolzano has created a group of five professors and two external members with specialization on ideation and market research to assessing funding options; producing business plans; and delivering new products to the market. The group has studied the best contract possible for hiring experts with relevant experience and motivation on creating and developing startups resulting in an appalto.

The team has also worked on the promotion of the pre-acceleration and acceleration activities. For the pre-acceleration phase, an unibz call for startups has been implemented during spring 2024. A business challenge jointly with Loacker and Junior Enterprise Alto Adige, and a conference on the creation of innovative enterprises in order to promote iNEST and the CC1 activities to unibz

environment have been run on September 2, 2024. Moreover, unibz has coordinated the participation of iNEST at Bolzano slush'd on September 3, 2024.

1.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN

Defining the optimal contract for all activities has proven challenging.

Firstly, regarding personnel, the standard post-doctoral position (assegni di ricerca) has been too restrictive to attract candidates with experience in startup project analysis. This may be due to a scarcity of individuals with such combined expertise and local competition from the NOI Techpark incubator. To address this, an "appalto" contract was utilized.

Secondly, for activities like participation in Bolzano's Slush'd, we encountered concerns that participation and sponsorship could be perceived as arbitrarily transferring of public funds to a private entity. Again, the "appalto" contract was employed as a solution. However, it's important to note that using the "appalto" model imposes a significant administrative burden on the institution and all involved parties.

In summary, unibz has faced considerable difficulties in transferring public funds to private partners while maintaining objectivity and impartiality. While the implemented solutions are robust in addressing these challenges, they are admittedly inefficient.

1.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES

The next steps for the 2025 activities relate to completing the team with analysts who possess advanced skills in startup composition, structure and future development.

Furthermore, the Free University of Bolzano is exploring the possibility of implementing a permanent program after the INEST project concludes. The three main challenges are: 1) establishing a network of motivated stakeholders; 2) identifying appropriate solutions in collaboration with partners; and 3) securing funding.

References

PNRR-iNEST Project and Start-ups (2204/09/02) "The New Role of Triveneto Universities in the Creation of Innovative Enterprises", NOI Techpark Auditorium A2.2.32, Bolzano.

2. SPOKE 2 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1

Spoke 2 activities focus on applied research and technology transfer related to the areas of health, wellness and healthy eating. These thematic areas are declined in the Spoke in a broad sense, including the related enabling infrastructures, both physical and digital, and the digital transformation of companies and entities operating in the related supply chains.

The Spoke's main mission is to enhance technological development and social innovation to promote the health and well-being of citizens and support the digital and green transition of the Triveneto social and health system. The Spoke will pursue this ambitious goal by combining the study, development, and testing of enabling sciences and technologies in various fields: from artificial intelligence to digital health, biotechnology, omics, electronics, and robotics. The project will not only deal with technology, but will properly take into consideration the relevant social, historical, economic and psychological context. The technologies developed will be integrated to contribute to the digital transformation of the socio-economic system in the Northeast, promoting innovative cures and treatments that can contribute to a healthy lifestyle and monitoring their impact on citizens and their quality of life.

Within the context of a citizen- and patient-centered framework, the objective of Spoke 2 is to foster technical and social innovation with the purpose of enhancing human health and well-being, as well as providing assistance to the transition of Triveneto health systems to digital and environmentally friendly practices. The ambitious overarching aim will be pursued by Spoke 2 by the utilization of enabling technologies and sciences, which include Artificial Intelligence, Digital Health, Biotechnology, Omic Technologies, Electronics, and Robotics. This will be done within the framework of social, historical, economic, and psychological factors. In order to contribute to the digital transformation of the socio-economic system of the Triveneto region, technologies will be incorporated. This will involve the promotion of innovative treatments and therapies for a healthy lifestyle, as well as the monitoring of the influence these technologies have on inhabitants and the quality of life they experience.

Within more specific reference to the Cross Cutting activity 1 – Support the generation and the development of research start-ups and spin-offs, the Spoke 2 promotes itself as a catalyst inside the university system to foster the creation of startups initiatives with business ideas related to health, food, and lifestyle. The is an important player in the context of innovation ecosystems, offering access to advanced research resources and aiding the incubation of breakthrough ideas.

The goal is to create real impacts in the form of new processes, products, and services that will strengthen the iNEST Ecosystem. The projects produced focus not just on issues of research and technology innovation, but also on assisting emerging businesses in developing innovation strategies. Spoke 2 strongly encourages the use of digital tools and technology in this context, including them into both research and development efforts and the new goods and services that come from them. This combination between academic research and entrepreneurial spirit within the institution generates a dynamic ecosystem that fosters the development and growth of new firms, contributing considerably to the innovation landscape.

2.1. SPOKE “2” CC1 OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW

(title of the task, brief description of the topics, participants, general organisation and planning, expected results)

Title: Cross-cutting Activity: Support the Generation and Development of Research Start-ups and Spin-offs [CC1] for the **Spoke 2:** Health, Food and Lifestyle

Research Topics: RT1 – Digital Health and Systems for the Citizens; RT2 – Biotechnologies and Pharmaceutical Technologies; RT3 – Devices for Health; RT4 – Food and Health

Participants: Prof. Alessandro Rossi (Spoke 2 CC1 Principal Investigator and Rector's Delegate on Business Support); Prof. Sandro Trento (School of Innovation - SOI Director); Prof. Erica Santini (Department of Economics and Management, Delegate for Internationalization); Prof. Andrea Caputo (Department of Economics and Management, Director of the Master in International Management)).

General Organization and Planning: At the University of Trento, key activities within Spoke 2: Health, Food, and Lifestyle will be a strategic mix of scouting and acceleration activities, aligned with the overarching design of an innovation ecosystem that supports the generation and development of research start-ups and spin-offs. This approach is characterized by a dual structure:

Firstly, the Pre-Acceleration phase will be managed in a decentralized yet coordinated manner across all SPOKES. This structure is essential for generating and selecting innovative ideas that can evolve into research start-ups and spin-offs. The decentralized aspect of this phase allows for direct support to emerging entrepreneurs, including students, PhD candidates, and researchers. Simultaneously, coordination across SPOKES ensures the replication of economies, the development of methodologies, and the creation of technological platforms that are applicable to all SPOKES, drawing from the best cases at each university.

Secondly, the Acceleration & Fundraising phases will be centrally managed. This phase is crucial for defining the business model of the research start-ups and spin-offs and managing investment rounds to facilitate market entry and scaling. Centralized management during these phases allows for economies of scale, utilizing methodologies and technological platforms that have been developed and tested.

At the University of Trento, the contribution to these phases will be twofold: local scouting activities will be carried out via a scouting specialist who will focus on identifying and nurturing promising ideas within the university. Additionally, the centralized acceleration activities will be supported through startup analysis, ensuring that the transition from idea to market is as smooth and efficient as possible, thereby enhancing the potential for successful market entry and growth of these ventures.

Also, the local research group will engage in regular meetings to coordinate efforts and ensure alignment of objectives. Additionally, regular interactions are planned with ecosystem stakeholders, including HIT and Trentino Sviluppo, as well as with other iNEST CC1 research units. This collaborative approach is designed to harness diverse expertise and resources for effective innovation and entrepreneurial growth.

Expected Results: The expected results include the successful establishment of an operational framework for innovation, the development of a skilled and informed pool of innovators through the execution of various awareness and pre-acceleration programs, and the effective identification and nurturing of potential startups and spin-offs in the subsequent acceleration and funding stages. This collective effort aims to result in tangible advancements in the research and development of health, food, and lifestyle-related technologies and solutions.

2.2. SPOKE “2” CCI TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES

List of CCI Tasks:

- CC1.1: Planning and validation
- **CC1.2: Pre-acceleration**
 - Sub Task CC1.2.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (10 Scouting specialists, one for each spoke - two for spoke 5, and pre-acceleration officer) of the pre-acceleration phase.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 9-40
 - Sub Task CC1.2.2: Implementation of the Scouting Stage to attract entrepreneurs-to-be from the university’s ecosystems and drive the research effort toward a proof-of-concept.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 10-23
 - Sub Task CC1.2.3: Implementation of the online Entrepreneurial training through Management & Educational Platform to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 12-26
 - Sub Task CC1.2.4: Open innovation activities. The objective of this task is to establish relationships with companies and other partners in order to facilitate the development of new projects, spinoffs and co-innovation activities between universities, startups and companies.
Responsible: UNIUD
Duration: months 9-40
- CC1.3: Acceleration
- CC1.4: Fundraising

Focus on Task CC1.2: Scouting and pre-acceleration activities in the Spoke “2”

Background: a series of initiatives at Unitrento are concerned with raising awareness on innovation and entrepreneurship among students and scholars. Central to these efforts is the School of Innovation (SOI), which offers interdisciplinary training blending technical, scientific, and humanistic approaches to innovation. The SOI's curriculum, enriched by the Crash Course in Intellectual Property Rights, equips participants with essential knowledge for ideating, validating and protecting innovation. Also, through initiatives like the Business Design program and the Start-Up Lab, participants gain practical skills in market analysis, business strategy, and human-centered design, laying a strong foundation for entrepreneurial ventures. The Proof of Concept (POC) program is reserved for patent holders and supports the efforts towards translating theoretical knowledge into viable, market-ready initiatives. The newly created Springboard of Startups program allows students to engage with stakeholders and

successful founders, both raising awareness on entrepreneurship and fostering the next generation of innovators. Collaboration with Hub Innovazione Trentino (HIT) further strengthens the university's capacity in technology transfer and innovation, bridging academic research with market opportunities through the participation in the Trentino Startup Valley program. These programs collectively act as a springboard for scouting and pre-acceleration activities, preparing participants not just in ideation but also in the practical aspects of launching and scaling innovative solutions in the competitive market of health and wellness.

State of the art: The theoretical and practical basis of Trento University's entrepreneurship and innovation activities are founded on a wide range of scholarly works and practice-based theories. This includes, but is not limited to, key contributions such as Lombardi and Berk's thoughts on "Startup Program Design," which provide useful frameworks for organizing entrepreneurial acceleration and incubation programs. Eric Ries' 'The Lean Startup' is another good example, demonstrating the importance of constant innovation in the entrepreneurial process. Additionally, among other resources, Steve Blank's 'The Four Steps to the Epiphany' and 'The Startup Owner's Manual,' co-authored with Bob Dorf, serve as significant tools, providing extensive strategies for starting and maintaining successful companies. In practical terms, in the above mentioned programs and initiatives, the university incorporates approaches such as design thinking, which encourages creative problem-solving and user-centered product development. The lean startup methodology and its validation concepts are critical in fostering a culture of quick prototyping and iterative testing, which is required for rapidly validating business ideas. Based on these beliefs, business modeling assists participants in developing viable business models, whereas effective thinking promotes an adaptive, resource-oriented approach to entrepreneurship. This combination of academic knowledge and practical approaches fosters innovation by leading participants from the early phases of idea development to the difficulties of establishing and scaling a firm.

Methodology: The scouting methodology employed in the Spoke 2 for identifying and nurturing entrepreneurial opportunities is a strategic mix of pull and push approaches. Actively hunting for ideas, the university engages in detailed interviews with researchers, conducts comprehensive mapping of research group efforts, and undertakes desk analysis of its existing portfolio of academic startups and patents. This proactive push approach is complemented by a pull strategy, where the university orchestrates various awareness and capacity-building activities such as courses, workshops, and seminars aimed at fostering an entrepreneurial mindset. Additionally, initiatives like open office hours and open call programs are implemented to encourage the spontaneous emergence of new ideas and ventures. This dual-method approach ensures a thorough and dynamic process of scouting, effectively tapping into both existing and latent entrepreneurial potential within the university community. Lastly, best practices in automated AI-based scouting and spinoff development are benchmarked.

Ongoing activities: To find and support innovation inside its ecosystem, Spoke 2 at the University of Trento has started a thorough series of scouting efforts. In order to provide a continuous perspective of the inventive outputs that are already available as well as possible areas for future development, these operations started with the careful mapping of patents and other Intellectual Resources (IRs). Concurrently, the university began a comprehensive mapping of research groups and main investigators with the goal of identifying both innovation hotspots and strategic research areas where the IP output and valorisation could be improved. This propaedeutic activity enables a tailored approach to foster existing entrepreneurial drivers and to stimulate the emergence of such drivers in underrepresented areas of competence. The university's methods are continually checked to make

sure they remain in line with worldwide standards of excellence through this process, which involves benchmarking against national and international best practices. In addition to these strategic objectives, the research group is conducting a detailed literature assessment and stakeholder interviews on scouting tactics in order to improve and develop its methodology. European and Italian excellence centres for academic entrepreneurship are mapped, thoroughly analysed, and whenever possible interviewed (usually in the persons of TTOs directives). Based on these analyses, key areas for improvement in best practices are identified and an improvement strategy is outlined. In parallel, entrepreneurial projects that are not accredited as academic spinoffs (i.e. prospective academic spinoffs and existing enterprises that did not undergo the accreditation process) are interviewed to understand key unmet needs and/or deterrent factors in the accreditation process. Consequently, the current regulation for accreditation of university spinoffs is being reviewed supporting the UniTN TTO personnel. Spoke 2 has initiated a number of programs to increase awareness and develop capacity for entrepreneurial engagement in tandem with these strategic goals. These consist of the Springboard of Startups (SOS) Program, the Business Design Program, the Business Growth Program, and the Crash Course on Intellectual Property Rights. Furthermore: the School of Innovation (SOI), which is actively attempting to cultivate an innovative and entrepreneurial culture among students and researchers, offers a comprehensive 12 ECTS curriculum in line with these goals.

Lastly, a number of AI-based tools are being tested for integration in the current scouting workflow and business design and validation support activities.

2.3. SPOKE “2” CCI DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES

(e.g., conferences, meetings, participation in kick-off and mid-term plenary sessions, overall working group activities, interaction with the stakeholders)

The Spoke 2 contributed to all the sessions of the workshop “*iNEST 2 - Knowledge transfer through Start-ups*”, supporting the definition of an agenda and an actionable plan to build on the foundations and collective momentum generated with the iNEST project.

The University of Trento and the School of Innovation patronised the “*Slush’d Bolzano 2024*” event, which brought together up to 1,000 participants, including startups, investors, corporate executives, and institutional representatives, to promote innovation and entrepreneurial ambition among the most influential stakeholders in the local, national, and international ecosystem.

The School of Innovation is contributing to the UniCredit’s “*Imprenditori #GenNext*” program, designing and delivering a 3-days masterclass in entrepreneurship for prospective graduates.

2.4. SPOKE “2” CCI MAIN RESULTS

(main results achieved till now, including pictures, photos, graphs, table, link to on-line material, etc...)

A number of meeting sessions have been organised with Hub Innovazione Trentino and Trentino Sviluppo to better define the roles and responsibilities of each partner in supporting local startups and academic spinoffs. This resulted in the definition of a clear pathway that local entrepreneurial initiatives can undertake to increase their maturity level, from the opportunity identification/ideation stage to the scaleup.

A standardized scouting process was successfully established by integrating literature research and benchmarking activities with Spoke 2’s best practices. This approach combined push and pull

strategies, including direct visits to research groups and broader awareness-raising initiatives such as entrepreneurship programs, workshops, events, and system-level communication plans.

The established scouting workflow resulted in the identification of 10 and 18 new startup ideas during the first and second scouting round, respectively. Of these, Algify, FEP (Finding Emerging Pathogens, Robotizr, and Novawalk entered the accelerator program.

A new, hybrid and extracurricular program - Springboard of Startups - has been designed and piloted during the first semester of the academic year 2024/25. This program combines networking and dissemination events with hands-on workshops, connecting students with successful founders and other relevant stakeholders of the existing innovation ecosystem. This allowed for the creation of a community of (proto)founders and entrepreneurs-to-be, counting more than 60 members with varying seniority and academic background.

2.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN

No new relevant problems arose during 2024, with the corrective actions outlined in the last report having succeeded in solving the identified issues- i.e. attracting a larger pool of talents for the recruitment of the Startup Analyst and Scouting Specialist. Therefore, the main organisational concern has been the recovery from the delays accumulated during 2024.

2.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES

(With reference to the 2025 activities)

In 2025 the actions of the Spoke 2 will focus on:

Optimisation and harmonisation of educational and awareness programs. To broaden the pool of prospective founders, both the newly created Springboard of Startups (SoS) will be further tailored to the needs of the engaged students and researchers. A steering committee composed of the Startup Analyst, the Scouting Specialist, a SOI professor, and three students/researchers has been created. This committee will re-adjust the program offer based on the feedback collected *in itinere*. Furthermore, SoS will be better harmonised to the educational offer at the School of Innovation, in order to support and empower existing programs and courses. This is expected to: a) reach talented individuals at the very early career stage, b) increase the number of perspective founders, and c) increase the university's output in terms of startup ideas and academic spinoffs.

Harmonisation of initiatives with HIT and TS. While the Trentino ecosystem is already well established, with several public agencies dedicated to supporting startups and developing the local economy, this sometimes is a source of confusion for academic founders. This is due to the pathway for commercial exploitation of IP, from the incorporation to the acceleration, and which agencies should be involved at which stage, being very clear to the stakeholders but overwhelming for prospective founders. The effort of co-designing such pathways and effectively communicating it to students and researchers is currently undergoing. This is expected to add clarity and facilitate and encourage founders in taking the entrepreneurial initiative. In parallel, this is also bound to harmonise KPIs across different stakeholders, further streamlining the process of supporting the emergence of innovative startups.

Revision of the University's spinoff regulation. The scouting process highlighted a number of entrepreneurial projects, some of which already incorporated and incubated/accelerated, that are generated within the University but are not accredited as academic spinoffs. The proponents of such projects, as well as prospective founders, are being interviewed to understand barriers and resistances that are deterring them from applying to the accreditation. In parallel, a benchmarking analysis is being performed to identify the best practices in Italian and European entrepreneurial universities. With the support of the university's TTO, these inputs are being used to review and identify key improvement areas in the university spinoff regulation. The improvement of the best practices in terms of support/benefits given to academic spinoffs is expected to increase the Spoke 2 output in terms of officially accredited spinoffs.

Exploration and piloting of new processes and tools. The Startup Analyst and Scouting Specialist have been dedicated in benchmarking best practices across Italian and European entrepreneurial universities. These include processes for venture creation and AI-based tools for integration in the current scouting workflow and business design and validation support activities. Specifically, the possibility of establishing an academic venture builder exploiting the university's pool of talents and knowledge is currently being explored. Supporting these efforts, a number of AI tools that are currently being used in TTOs of European entrepreneurial universities are currently being tested and selected for integration into the established scouting process.

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3. SPOKE 3 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1

The research activities of Spoke 3, coordinated by the University of Udine, focus on promoting innovation and facilitating a green and digital transition in the advanced manufacturing sector. The research activities follow 5 thematic areas, or research topics (RT):

- RT1: Energy
- RT2: Smart manufacturing, Mechatronics and Robotics
- RT3: Materials
- RT4: Artificial Intelligence and Data Science
- RT5: Organizational, economical and legal aspects

Within the iNEST project, cross-cutting activity 1 is crucial for ensuring a coordinated and integrated approach across all Spokes within the iNEST project. This activity, operating within an innovation ecosystem framework, aims to enhance the value of innovative ideas stemming from Spoke 3 research. It facilitates the establishment and growth of research-based startups and spin-offs.

3.1. SPOKE 3 CC1 OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW

(title of the task, brief description of the topics, participants, general organisation and planning, expected results)

As already mentioned, the main objective of CC1 is to support the generation and development of startups and spin-offs coming from the academic community. This goal characterizes the whole cross cutting activity and it is common to all Spokes, regardless of the specific research topic each University focuses on.

In continuity with the first cycle of CC1, the same quantitative goals listed below were maintained.

- **Pre-screening:** collection of at least 10 ideas coming from each Spoke
- **Screening:** selection of at least 8 ideas, through a pre-screening process
- **Committee Evaluation:** selection of at least 4 ideas, through a screening process, to be supported in the preparation of the pitch to be presented during the Selection Day.

3.2. SPOKE 3 CC1 TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES

List of CC1 Tasks:

- CC1.1: Planning and validation
- **CC1.2: Pre-acceleration**
 - Sub Task CC1.2.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (10 Scouting specialists, one for each spoke - two for spoke 5, and pre-acceleration officer) of the pre-acceleration phase.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 9-40

- Sub Task CC1.2.2: Implementation of the Scouting Stage to attract entrepreneurs-to-be from the university's ecosystems and drive the research effort toward a proof-of-concept.
 Responsible: UNIVE
 Duration: months 10-23
 - Sub Task CC1.2.3: Implementation of the online Entrepreneurial training through Management & Educational Platform to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
 Responsible: UNIVE
 Duration: months 12-26
 - Sub Task CC1.2.4: Open innovation activities. the objective of this task is to establish relationships with companies and other partners in order to facilitate the development of new projects, spinoffs and co-innovation activities between universities, startups and companies.
 Responsible: UNIUD
 Duration: months 9-40
- **CC1.3: Acceleration**
 - Sub Task CC1.3.1: Development of the Key Standardized Elements (Acceleration Framework; Acceleration Physical Spaces) of the acceleration phase to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
 Responsible: UNIVR
 Duration: months 11-34
 - Sub Task CC1.3.2: Engagement and coordination of the Key Actors (Acceleration officer, 2 StartUp Analysts) of the acceleration phase.
 Responsible: UNIVR
 Duration: months 14-40
 - Sub Task CC1.3.3: Implementation of the Acceleration phase through Pitch Building & Pitch Session, sprint program and Demo Day. The objective of this phase is to bring the start-ups to validate the market and a scalable business model.
 Responsible: UNIVR
 Duration: months 15-32
 - CC1.4: Fundraising

Focus on Task CC1.2: Scouting and pre-acceleration activities within Spoke 3

Background / State of the Art: During the reporting period, the working group established within Spoke 3 at the beginning of the first cycle was consolidated, increasing the interactions and the efficiency of the collaboration between its members. The working group includes the Open Innovation Manager (Enrico Pusceddu), the Scouting Specialist (Eduardo Canaku), their scientific supervisor (Professor Cinzia Battistella), UNIUD Representative for the Cross Cutting activity CC1 (Professor Piergiorgio Comuzzo), and the Delegate of the Rector for Technology Transfer (Professor

Giovanni Cortella). The working group continued to cooperate closely with all the offices supporting research activities (Technology Transfer, Intellectual Property, Project Planning, Administrative). There are also strong interactions with the Spoke's affiliated partners (POLOAA and FINN), leveraging on their expertise as startup incubators.

Methodology: According to the methodology discussed with the coordinator of CC1, scouting and pre-acceleration activities adhered to the Pre-acceleration funnel, designed by the Scouting Officer and his Assistants, which consists in Pre-screening, Screening, Committee Evaluation, as briefly described in paragraph 2.1.

As part of the initiative "Start Cup Udine", Spoke 3 has carried out scouting and pre-acceleration activities, in particular regarding Sub Task CC1.2.2.

With this respect, startup projects who applied to the call had the opportunity to participate to events and training sessions concerning several dimensions of entrepreneurship and startup development, organized as follows:

- Phase 1: Team and Idea definition
 - o Team Composition I
 - o Team Composition II
 - o Idea Definition I
 - o Idea Definition II
 - o Team Building
- Phase 2: Pitch Preparation
 - o Pitch Preparation I
 - o Pitch Preparation II
- Phase 3: Business Plan Preparation
 - o Business Plan fundamentals
 - o Market Analysis I
 - o Market Analysis II
 - o Financial Plan
 - o Funding Opportunities for Startups + study visit to TEC4I FVG
 - o Idea Execution + study visit to PoloAA
 - o Public Speaking

Participants presented their projects during the final event of the "Start Cup Udine" initiative, which took place in Udine on October 28, 2024.

Some of the participants were included in the Pre-Acceleration Funnel of iNEST CC1, together with other projects coming from the Spoke's affiliated partners (POLOAA and FINN). The final step of the Pre-Acceleration phase is represented by the Selection Day, in which all the startup projects who passed the Committee Evaluation were presented to the CC1 Committee and an external jury. The Selection Day of the 2nd cycle was held at the University of Udine on December 3, 2024. Sixteen teams were selected for the Acceleration phase.

Ongoing activities: The activities related to Scouting and Pre-acceleration phase are now concluded, after the Selection Day of the second cycle. However, some activities related to the diffusion of the entrepreneurial culture in the academic community will be planned and implemented, in order to promote and support the main objective of CCI, namely the generation and the development of science-based startup and spin-offs.

Focus on Task CCI.3: Acceleration activities within Spoke 3

Background / State of the Art: A centralized Acceleration program has been developed. It employs a holistic approach to innovation, leveraging synergies between academic research and the business world. This centralized program provides selected teams with the necessary training to develop robust business models and to prepare effective pitch decks. The Acceleration program culminates with the Demo Day, a public event where startups have the opportunity to present their project to potential investors.

Methodology: The Acceleration program features a series of workshops combining theoretical knowledge with practical applications in innovation and entrepreneurship, together with pitch sessions to enhance presentation skills. Workshops are based on the lean startup methodology and they leverage peer learning, allowing participants to learn from each other by sharing experiences, challenges, and solutions.

Moreover, every startup is assigned two coaches, professionals from universities and institutions who help them apply what learned in workshops to their specific start-up contexts. Coaches follow start-up teams during the workshops and organize one-on-one periodic coaching sessions. The scouting specialist of Spoke 3 was involved in the program as a coach, together with other scouting specialists and startup professionals.

In addition to in-person workshops, the program included also 5 webinars, held by experts in specific vertical fields.

To summarize, the first cycle of the Acceleration program consisted in the following activities:

- Workshop #1: April 19–20, 2024, in Trieste (UniTS): “Strategy innovation and problem-client fit”.
- Workshop #2: May 10–11, 2024, in Padua: “Solution and market fit”.
- Workshop #3: May 31–June 1, 2024, in Trento: “Profit model” and a pitch session test.
- Workshop #4: June 28–29, 2024, in Trieste (SISSA): “Go to market strategy”.
- Workshop #5: August 30–31, 2024, in Verona: “Funding strategy”.
- Pitch Clinic: September 20, 2024, in Venice.
- Webinar #1: Presentation of psychological profiles (June 19, 2024) by Beniamino Mirisola;
- Webinar #2: Marketing, customer acquisition, sales (June 24, 2024) by Giacomo Tesolin;
- Webinar #3: IP strategy (July 5, 2024) by Elisa Toniolo;
- Webinar #4: Establishment of an innovative S.r.l. between civil and tax regulations (September 13, 2024) by Valter Carturo;
- Webinar #5: Innovative start-ups and contractual frameworks (September 27, 2024) by Paolo Guaragnella and Giorgio Abbadessa.

Ongoing activities: The second cycle of the Acceleration program is starting, and it will follow a path similar to the first one, except from some adjustments designed to optimize it. It will include the following in-person workshops.

- Workshop #1: January 17–18, 2025, in Trento: “Introduction and presentation of the strategic plan”.
- Workshop #2: February 7–8, 2025, in Verona: “Problem, current solutions, and proposition”.
- Workshop #3: February 28–March 1, 2025, in Udine: “Market and competition”.
- Workshop #4: March 14–15, 2025, in Venice (Ca’ Foscari): “Governance, vision, mission, and strategy; Business Model”.
- Pitch Clinic #1: April 4, 2025, in Venice (Iuav).
- Workshop #5: May 9–10, 2025, in Bolzano: “Action plan & eco-fin plan”.
- Workshop #6: May 23–24, 2025, in Trieste: “Eco-fin plan & funding”.
- Pitch Clinic #2: June 6, 2025, in Verona.

3.3. SPOKE 3 CCI DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES

(e.g., conferences, meetings, participation in kick-off and mid-term plenary sessions, overall working group activities, interaction with the stakeholders)

During the reporting period, several coordination meetings were convened to facilitate effective communication and ensure optimal synchronization among all the various teams involved in the project. These meetings were held in conjunction with the in-person workshops of the Acceleration program. They provided a crucial opportunity for discussing action plans, progress made, assessing emerging challenges, and formulating collaborative strategies to be adopted. These frequent meetings permitted to develop a common methodology for the scouting and Pre-acceleration phase, still allowing each Spoke to adjust the strategies to its specific characteristics.

In addition, as previously mentioned, some events and visits were organized by Spoke 3. They were aimed at raising the awareness of entrepreneurship through talks, speeches and success stories from startups coming.

Corresponding posters can be found below.

CALL FOR IDEAS!

Partecipa a Start Cup Udine

Hai un'idea d'impresa nel cassetto? Vorresti sviluppare le tue ricerche in forma d'impresa?

Cerchi delle competenze o un team per concretizzare il tuo progetto di business?

Hai delle competenze che ritieni utili per un'impresa?

Proponi le tue idee! Sono aperte le iscrizioni!

Partecipa al training innovativi, prepara il pitch e presenta la tua idea d'impresa!

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- Climate Change (Green & Blue)
- Imprenditoria femminile

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- martedì 7 maggio, ore 12.30 Aula C9, Rizzi, Udine
- mercoledì 8 maggio, ore 8.30 Aula A, Via Tomadini, Udine

PER INFO
<https://www.startcup.it/it/serveizi/impresa/punte-impresa/startcup-udine/impresa/startcup-udine-forma-selection-day>

Selection Day

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ore 14.30

Auditorium Biblioteca Scientifica e Tecnologica
via F. Schiavi 44, Udine

Presentazione dei progetti partecipanti a Start Cup Udine e premiazioni

PROGRAMMA

ore 14.30
Saluti introduttivi
Giovanni Cortella
Università degli Studi di Udine
Modera
Alessandra Salvatori
Teleferrati

Presentazione progetti finalisti

ISCRIZIONI
<https://www.startcup.it/it/serveizi/impresa/punte-impresa/startcup-udine/forma-selection-day>

Intervento
Daniele De Angelis
Business development, Invitalia
Invitato a sostegno delle Startups
Servizi, strumenti e incentivi per la tua idea d'impresa

ore 18
Premiazioni
Aperitivo di networking

Moreover, as part of the activities, two visits were organized. Participants to the initiative Start Cup Udine had the opportunity to visit Spoke 3's affiliated partners, TEC4I FVG and Polo Tecnologico Alto Adriatico, having the chance to understand how startup incubators work, exploring potential future collaborations and opportunities.

Finally, as already mentioned, the Selection Day of the first cycle was held in Udine.

Selection Day – 2° ciclo

Cross-Cutting Activity 1 – Support to the generation and the development of start-ups and spin-offs

Martedì 3 dicembre
dalle 9:00 alle 17:05

Università degli Studi di Udine
Biblioteca Scientifica e Tecnologica
Via Fausto Schiavi n°44, 33100, Udine

Negli ultimi mesi, lo Scouting Team della Cross-Cutting Activity 1 di iNEST ha raccolto, in sinergia con le Università e gli istituti di ricerca, oltre 170 idee science-based innovative da trasformare in progetti di startup. Ricercatrici e ricercatori, membri di startup pre-seed, dottorandi, studentesse e studenti sono stati coinvolti per valorizzare i loro sforzi di ricerca e perfezionare le loro idee di business.

Ora è arrivato il momento cruciale: durante il Selection Day, il Comitato della CCI e una giuria esterna selezioneranno le idee più promettenti, che verranno ammesse al secondo ciclo del programma di Accelerazione di iNEST.

Programma

9:00	Accoglienza e registrazione	13:00	Pausa pranzo
9:30	Saluti istituzionali e introduzione Piergiorgio Comuzza, Carlo Bagnoli	14:00	Terza sessione di pitch (8 startup)
9:45	Presentazione del programma di Accelerazione David Tacconi, Andrea Marella	15:30	Coffee break
10:00	Prima sessione di pitch (7 startup)	15:50	Quarta sessione di pitch (7 startup)
11:10	Coffee break	17:05	Chiusura
11:30	Seconda sessione di pitch (8 startup)	Dalle 17:00 alle 19:00, il Comitato della CCI si riunirà per decretare quali progetti saranno ammessi al 2° ciclo del programma di Accelerazione di iNEST.	

3.4. SPOKE 3 CCI MAIN RESULTS

(main results achieved till now, including pictures, photos, graphs, table, link to on-line material, etc...)

The following table summarizes the expected outcomes, agreed with the coordinator and the Steering Committee, and the actual results obtained by Spoke 3.

Expected Outcome	Target Goal	First cycle	Second cycle
Pre-screening: Ideas/projects collected for the Pre-screening phase	10+	20	23
Screening: Ideas/projects selected for the Screening phase	8+	8	10
Committee evaluation: Ideas/projects submitted to the Committee	4+	5	5
Selection Day: ideas/projects pitched during the Selection Day	-	2	5
Acceleration Program: ideas/projects admitted to the Acceleration Program	-	1	2

3.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN

(Bullet points and brief summary, administration topics)

One significant obstacle to the research activities consisted in the engagement of the academic community in entrepreneurial activities. Often, in the traditional academic reward system research publications and scholarly impact are prioritized. This can lead to a lack of incentive for faculty and researchers to actively pursue entrepreneurship and commercial valorization of their research findings, as it may not be viewed as equally valuable within their academic career paths.

3.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES

(With reference to the 2025 activities)

In 2025, Spoke 3 aims at actively promoting and supporting the primary goal of CCI, namely the generation and development of science-based startups and spin-offs. With this respect, specific initiatives will be planned and implemented to foster an entrepreneurial culture within the academic community.

4. SPOKE 4 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1

The main objective of Spoke 4 is to ally all the stakeholders participating in the built environment transformation to overcome the current challenges and adapt to social, economic and climate changes. Hence, the Spoke has the chance of becoming the node connecting all the sub-systems of the territorial transformation, promoting a collaborative and synergistic network between all the supply chain and sector operators: academic research, design practice, manufacturing, construction, commerce and distribution, the credit system, and public administrations.

- **RT1 - Strategic plan for the development of the construction and sustainable design sectors.** RT1 developed an analysis of the built environment while maintaining a transcale approach. RT1 identified the main sustainability objectives for the following building phase in Italy, the first to transform the built environment non-expansively;
- **RT2 - Technological solutions for the construction and sustainable design sectors,** RT2 identified an innovative method for selecting the survey areas according to the most sensitive territory for each topic and tested the technique in eleven different sites;
- **RT3 - Interaction between environments and human beings in the construction and sustainable design sectors.** In the first year, it aimed to identify the most critical issues regarding collective and individual well-being. The first year acted as a pivot in managing relations between general studies in the Northeast;

In this scientific context, **cross-cutting activity 1** is essential in fostering entrepreneurship education and dissemination within university ecosystems, connecting the business world with the scientific community to maintain a collaborative network over time.

One of the goals is to integrate research institutes to interact with the regional context, with the ultimate goal of contributing to creating a market economy through continuous trade and synergistic interactions.

4.1. SPOKE 4 CROSS-CUTTING ACTIVITY 1 OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW

Within the iNEST Consortium, Cross-Cutting Activity 1 aims to foster the development and selection of innovative ideas arising from the scientific work of Spoke 4, with the ultimate goal of transforming them into research start-ups and spin-offs. To achieve this, CCI is structured into four specific phases:

- **CCI.1: Planning and validation:** planning was completed in March 2023. Validation and periodical reviews are ongoing till the end of the project.
- **CCI.2: Pre-Acceleration:** The first pre-acceleration round concluded (April 2024 – September 2024), as did the second pre-acceleration round (June 2024 – December 2024).. (task leader: UniVE)
- **CCI.3: Acceleration:** The first acceleration cycle (April 2024 – September 2024) has concluded, while the second cycle is about to begin, starting in mid-January 2025 and ending in June 2025. (task leader: UniVR)
- **CCI.4: Fundraising:** The first Fundraising cycle is occurring (task leader: UniTS)

The objectives of Task **CCI.1** were concluded by outlining common actions for all participating spokes. A common strategy was provided for all 9 spokes, planned through scheduled meetings and constant communication through online data-sharing platforms.

The first two **pre-acceleration (CCI.2)** rounds have successfully concluded, coordinated by Dr. Serena Ruffato, the scouting specialist hired under a contract effective March 1. Dr. Ruffato spearheaded the call for startup pre-seed initiatives for Spoke 4, conducting extensive scouting activities within the Università Iuav di Venezia through various initiatives and events. Spoke 4 capitalized on the strong reputation of the Start.Hub Iuav program—a well-established idea acceleration pathway at Iuav—to attract, refine, and select 10–15 promising ideas per cycle.

In the first **Acceleration (CCI.3)** cycle, two startups proposed by Spoke 4 were selected: Re-Hub and ARGO. Re-Hub advanced to the fourth **Fundraising** phase (**CCI.4**), where it received the special prize awarded by Gellify during the investor day.

4.2. SPOKE 4 CROSS-CUTTING ACTIVITY 1 TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES

List of CC1 Tasks:

- CC1.1: Planning and validation
- CC1.2: Pre-acceleration
 - Sub Task CC1.2.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (10 Scouting specialists, one for each spoke - two for spoke 5, and pre-acceleration officer) of the pre-acceleration phase.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 9-40
 - Sub Task CC1.2.2: Implementation of the Scouting Stage to attract entrepreneurs-to-be from the university's ecosystems and drive the research effort toward a proof-of-concept.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 10-23
 - Sub Task CC1.2.3: Implementation of the online Entrepreneurial training through Management & Educational Platform to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 12-26
 - Sub Task CC1.2.4: Open innovation activities. the objective of this task is to establish relationships with companies and other partners to facilitate the development of new projects, spinoffs and co-innovation activities between universities, startups and companies.
Responsible: UNIUD
Duration: months 9-40
- CC1.3: Acceleration
- CC1.4: Fundraising

Focus on Task CCI.2: Scouting and pre-acceleration activities in the Spoke 4

Background / State of the Art:

Since 2017, Iuav has organized a training and idea-acceleration program for students, alumni, PhD students, researchers and collaborators every year.

The goal is to enhance ideas born within undergraduate, doctoral or master's workshops with high business potential and/or elevated technological and innovative value and turn them into academic spinoffs.

The program is structured in two phases:

1. Startup School - training course on entrepreneurship

The training activity is aimed at entrepreneurial alphabetization through analysing successful cases, good practices and opportunities emerging from society. The focus is on assessing the impact of the idea on the context and the importance of the team for the technical and economic sustainability of the project. Startup school is organized, with open meetings for everyone to attend. Course attendance allows students to earn university credits and LinkedIn badges.

Classes are held in-person and online and involve expert teachers in business and startups. Face-to-face training sessions are alternated with workshop sessions for analysis and development of ideas, encouraging cross-fertilization among participants. CEOs of experienced and successful startups are also invited to bring their experience and feedback.

2. Start.Hub - ideas acceleration program

A maximum of 12/14 teams, formed/consolidated during the Startup School training period, will access the second part of the program. Every team must meet specific criteria: have an innovative idea, consist of at least two members, and one must be affiliated (in the present or the past) with IUAV.

The course includes project work days, which are divided into groups and supported by a mentor who follows all stages of project development. The last meeting is structured as an intensive residential workshop, alternating face-to-face didactic activities, group analytical work, and one-on-one meetings with experts in marketing, business, administration, IT, user experience, product, patent, legal, etc.

At the end of the course, there is a pitch competition in which teams present their ideas and prototypes to an audience of investors, institutions and companies that decide the five winners who are awarded a cash prize to invest in the business idea.

Methodology:

In the first pre-acceleration cycle, 10 ideas/startups were created from the two 2022/23 editions of Start.Hub was proposed, and in the second cycle, the Scouting Specialist implemented a series of targeted activities to disseminate and gather more ideas.

The pre-acceleration funnel shared horizontally among all the Spokes of CCI is divided into the following steps:

1. **Target engagement, Scouting and Pre-screening.** Are performed by Scouting Specialists.
2. **Screening and Committee evaluation.** The scouting specialists suggest a short list of 4/5 startups. The CCI Committee selected 40 teams among the 9 Spokes.
3. **Selection Day.** During the Selection Day, all start-up projects from all Spokes that passed the Committee evaluation are presented to the CCI Committee (and a possible external jury, in the case of the 2nd cycle). The Committee then selects about 10-15 teams for the Acceleration phase.

Spoke 4 adapted the Start.Hub idea acceleration program to align with the terms and timelines of the iNEST CCI funnel, using it as a tool available to the scouting specialist for selecting the best business ideas within its spoke:

To enhance target engagement, the "Start.Hub LAB" was established as a dedicated physical space within the luav University. This space is a permanent hub for connecting with individuals interested in the initiative. In addition to receiving ongoing online support, current and aspiring entrepreneurs can benefit from an environment designed for exchanging ideas and fostering discussions among scouting specialists, students, and other stakeholders. To further promote the initiative, the CCI team has organized a series of presentations within bachelor's, master's, and doctoral programs, actively involving professors and students.

Nov 23 - Gen 24 > The [call for ideas](#) was opened in November 2023 and remained open until early February 2024. The call for ideas was disseminated through the institutional channels of iNEST and the Università Luav di Venezia, with the support of the technology transfer office. The call for ideas collected 206 expressions of interest from students, alumni, and researchers interested in exploring themes related to self-entrepreneurship.

Feb 24 - Mar 24 > Through the [Startup School](#), an integral part of the Start.Hub Luav program, more than 140 participants were trained through lessons on self-entrepreneurship, idea analysis using the design thinking methodology, and facilitating the matching of participants to form heterogeneous and multidisciplinary teams. The Scouting Specialist coordinated the activities with the support of a team of teachers, mentors and experts. The Startup School generated around 30 business ideas.

Apr 24 - Sep 24 > The top 10 ideas from the Startup School were selected for the [Start.Hub](#) acceleration program and were paired with mentors and experts who focused on deepening the business idea's potential, analyzing competitors, preparing a pitch deck, and drafting an executive summary of the project idea. At the end of the program, the 10 teams competed in a pitch competition, which determined the top 3 business ideas. The event was held at the Ca Tron Luav campus and was attended by several members of the iNEST CCI committee, who served as judges.

Oct 24 > The [immersive week](#) is an innovative initiative designed to help mature the best ideas from Start.Hub, making them more solid and competitive for the iNEST CCI committee selection at the Selection Day. The workshop involved five selected teams (the three finalists of the 2024 edition and two teams from the previous edition) who participated in a four-day residential program alongside industry experts, academics, and startups. The workshop included public speaking, business models, and digital innovation training sessions. The training was enriched by team-building activities and mentorship aimed at transforming ideas into competitive business models. The five projects cover various topics, from improving housing well-being for Generation Z with AI-based solutions (Arkea) to the participatory redesign of abandoned villages (Borgozero). FARMA 282 supports the Italian fashion system with a job placement platform for businesses and creatives, while Maetis develops technologies to accelerate the pre-diagnosis of learning disorders. Finally, Selvatica proposes seed tablets to regenerate urban green areas with native plants, promoting biodiversity.

Nov 24 > The scouting specialist supported the five teams in preparing their pitch decks for the selection day.

Only one of the five projects, Farma 282, successfully passed the selection for the selection day. Unfortunately, none of the startups proposed by Spoke 4 advanced to the acceleration phase.

Focus on Task CCI.3: Acceleration activities within Spoke 4

Background/State of the Art

In the first cycle, two of the ten startups presented by Spoke 4 were selected to participate in the training and acceleration program coordinated across all the Spokes in the Triveneto region.

Re-Hub and Argo actively participated in all the training sessions held in the area. They benefited from the support of tutors and instructors to improve their pitch decks and refine the business models of their entrepreneurial ideas. The first cycle concluded with the Demo Day in Verona on October 25, 2024. A panel of seven investors evaluated the ideas. Re-Hub was awarded the special prize offered by Gellify.

Methodology:

The acceleration program was structured as a series of monthly two-day in-person meetings (Friday and Saturday), hosted on a rotational basis at one of the locations provided by each Spoke. Below is the schedule of meetings for the first round of acceleration:

- Workshop #1: April 19–20, 2024, in Trieste (UniTS): “Strategy innovation and problem-client fit”.
- Workshop #2: May 10–11, 2024, in Padua: “Solution and market fit”.
- Workshop #3: May 31–June 1, 2024, in Trento: “Profit model” and a pitch session test.
- Workshop #4: June 28–29, 2024, in Trieste (SISSA): “Go to market strategy”.
- Workshop #5: August 30–31, 2024, in Verona: “Funding strategy”.
- Pitch Clinic: September 20, 2024, in Venice.
- Demo Day: October 25, 2024, in Verona

Ongoing activities: As for Sub-task CCI.3.3, the 2nd cycle of the Acceleration program is about to begin. All appointments, apart from the Demo Day, have been scheduled.

In the second cycle, Spoke 4 is not represented by any startup.

The scouting specialist will attend the in-person sessions to network and support the accelerated teams.

4.3. SPOKE 4 CROSS-CUTTING ACTIVITY 1 DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES

To strengthen scouting activities and the dissemination of activities, specific interventions have been planned within the design laboratories of IUAV University. The interventions aimed to disseminate the Start Hub 2023 path and what activities can be undertaken at the end of it.

Traditional engagement techniques were chosen for scouting: one-on-one meetings, events with the doctoral school to raise awareness of PhDs, PhD students and research fellows, and events and dissemination in classrooms.

The most significant dissemination events are listed below:

- CCI Event: **Selection Day**
<https://www.consorzioinest.it/inest-nuove-startup-in-arrivo/>
March 19, 2024 - Ca' Tron, Iuav University of Venice (Venice)

Spoke 4 hosted and coordinated the activities related to the first CCI Selection Day. During the event, 30 startups selected during the preliminary scouting phase were presented to the CCI committee. Among them, three startups proposed by Spoke 4 had the opportunity to demonstrate: Re-Hub and Argo (which were then selected for the acceleration phase) and Selvatica.

- Open Event: **"Verso il percorso di accelerazione iNEST"**
<https://www.iuav.it/cineca/sites/default/files/2024-09/Locandina%20iNEST.pdf>
September 24, 2024 - Ca' Tron, Iuav University of Venice (Venice)

The awards event for the best ideas participating in the Start.Hub Iuav training program took place, where a jury of experts and members of the iNEST CCI committee selected the four best ideas that earned access to the intensive residential workshop:

"Arkea," the project that uses artificial intelligence to provide suggestions for improving living spaces; "Mætis," is a technology designed to support, simplify, and accelerate the pre-diagnosis phase of learning disorders; "BorgoZero," which aims to revitalize abandoned villages through crowdfunding campaigns; "Nestify," which proposes making housing more accessible to university students by utilizing spaces during their absence.

- Networking Event: **"The Future in Acceleration: From Idea to Startup"**
<https://www.consorzioinest.it/il-futuro-in-accelerazione-dallidea-alla-start-up/>
September 26, 2024 - COMBO (Venezia)

Spoke 4 organized a joint event to facilitate matching ideas and skills among aspiring entrepreneurs in the Venetian area. The event took place at COMBO Venezia, with the participation of many startups from the two universities. It was an opportunity to hear testimonies from Re-Hub and h4Uni, finalists of the first acceleration cycle and to facilitate matching between the teams from Ca' Foscari University and those from the Università Iuav di Venezia.

- Networking Event: **“Startup Pizza: innovazione e networking una fetta alla volta”**
<https://www.consorzioinest.it/startup-pizza-innovazione-e-networking-una-fetta-alla-volta/>

October 27, 2024 -, Villa Angaran San Giuseppe (Bassano del Grappa, Vicenza)

The opening event of the intensive residential workshop features the startups selected by Spoke 4. The goal of the evening was to invite enthusiasts, industry experts, and curious attendees to engage directly with the teams and their ideas, offering grassroots feedback and advice. This exercise was valuable for fostering empathy with the direct stakeholders of the proposed products/services and for assessing the alignment of the value proposition with the target audience. The event was organized with the research fellow coordinating the Cross-Cutting Activity CC4, "Public Engagement," within Spoke 4. This demonstrated that cross-disciplinary activities between different CCs within Spoke can generate new insights and foster positive synergies.

- Workshop: **“Da Start.Hub a Start-up verso il percorso di accelerazione iNEST”**
<https://www.consorzioinest.it/da-start-hub-a-start-up/>

October 27-30, 2024 -Villa Angaran San Giuseppe (Bassano del Grappa, Vicenza)

5 startups selected within Start.Hub, the idea acceleration program, participated in the residential continuous training workshop. Four days of full immersion to deepen and analyze their business projects, supported by experts and instructors from the startup and entrepreneurship world. During the workshop, there were alternating educational sessions, one-on-one review meetings with experts, hands-on activities, encounters with successful startups, and team-building experiences.

4.4. SPOKE 4 CROSS-CUTTING ACTIVITY 1 MAIN RESULTS

One of the most interesting outcomes is related to the direct **collaboration between Spoke 4 and Spoke 6 (UniVE)**. Notably, a positive synergy developed between the respective scouting specialists, who coordinated during the pre-screening and screening phases to facilitate cross-pollination between the teams of the two spokes. This collaboration took place not only through joint events (The Future in Acceleration and Startup Pizza) but also by actively participating in the selection procedures in a coordinated manner. This type of synergy allowed for the exchange of skills and knowledge between the two spokes (and thus the two universities), typically focused on very different areas of expertise.

A second positive outcome was generated by creating a **coordination team** that involved the **research fellows responsible for the four cross-cutting activities** within Spoke 4. In particular, the scouting specialist benefited from the experience and support of fellow researchers in organizing events dedicated to startups (such as Startup Pizza). Spoke 4 will continue to pursue this idea of cross-pollination by organizing joint and cross-disciplinary events in the future involving CC1, CC2, CC3, and CC4.

The most significant outcome was the important **recognition awarded to the startup ReHub**, which successfully passed through the committee's entire scouting, screening, and evaluation process, ultimately being awarded during the Selection Day event on October 25th in Verona. **ReHub** received the award for the best device from Gellify. The startup, based in Murano (Venice), adds new value to non-recyclable glass waste by transforming it into a workable paste, which is then used to create a wide range of innovative solutions for architecture and design. These are mono-material products entirely made from secondary raw materials (free from plastics or resins), following the principles of the circular economy. News: <https://www.consorzioinest.it/5-startup-del-programma-di-accelerazione-premiate-da-una-giuria-di-investitori/>

4.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN

The scouting activities for the second round were much more structured than the first, following a well-defined workflow that allowed for broader audience engagement.

However, while the startups selected and presented during the first round of pre-screening were already well-established with solid business foundations, the TRL (Technology Readiness Level) and BRL (Business Readiness Level) of the business ideas gathered in the second round were insufficient to compete with the proposals from other Spokes. None of these ideas managed to pass the screening phase.

The data collected during the Call for Ideas highlights the strong interest of Spoke 4's target audience in the world of startups. However, while the Design Thinking methodology is familiar and easily comprehensible for this audience, the lack of solid theoretical preparation

in business and self-entrepreneurship often acts as a barrier for many students, hindering the transformation of academic projects into entrepreneurial ideas.

The synergy of know-how between students from diverse disciplines could pave the way for entrepreneurial projects with high technological content, significant growth potential, and scalability—key attributes for successful startups. Spoke 4 engaged in extensive discussions with Spoke 6 (UniVE) to explore ways to strengthen collaboration and skill exchange between the two universities. The goal is to foster more heterogeneous teams by blending project and design expertise with business planning and technology competencies, thereby enhancing future proposals' competitiveness.

4.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES

Spoke 4 will support and mentor the startup Re-Hub during its recently initiated fundraising phase. Additionally, the startup will collaborate with the laboratories of Luav University of Venice to conduct a series of technical material tests. These tests aim to enable the company to certify its production process and scale its business model effectively.

For the second cycle of CCI, the primary objective will be to strengthen the startups that did not pass the pre-selection phase by providing tailored support to refine and develop their business models. Meanwhile, the Scouting Specialist will be available to support the pre-selected teams during the acceleration program shared between the spokes.

5. SPOKE 5 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the Cross-Cutting Activity 1

The main topic of research and activities of Spoke 5 is **'Smart and Sustainable environments (manufacturing working, living)'** and addresses current issues in the manufacturing, working and living sectors. These are supported and enhanced by three Research Topics (RTs), namely:

- **RT1 - New and Emerging Technologies for Human Centric Manufacturing and other industrial working environment**
- **RT2 - Digital Twin in Industries 5.0**
- **RT3 - People, organization, and processes for Industry 5.0**
- **RT4 - Personalized Assistive Technologies and Smart Environments for Inclusive Living in private and public spaces**

Within this scientific framework, Cross-Cutting Activity 1 holds a pivotal role in promoting a coordinated and transversal strategy throughout all Spokes of the iNEST project. In line with the innovation ecosystem model, its primary focus is to enhance the value of innovative ideas generated by Spoke 5's research activities while also supporting the creation and growth of research-based startups and spin-offs. While the research activities of Spoke 5 primarily focus on the interplay between digitalization and sustainability across various environments, the support for startups and spin-offs has also generated spill-over effects into adjacent fields, such as digital technologies applied to healthcare and biosciences.”

5.1. SPOKE 5 CC1 OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW

Cross-Cutting Activity 1 within the iNEST Consortium aims to foster the generation and selection of innovative ideas stemming from Spoke 5's scientific work, transforming them into research startups and spin-offs. To achieve this, CC1 is structured into four distinct phases.

The initial phase focused on planning and validating all activities, which included recruiting Pier Luigi Franceschini and Alessio Cuccu as a dedicated resources to implement the committee's strategy for CC1. At present, the first cycle of CC1 is nearing completion, with the Fundraising phase underway.

Two startup projects originally selected through the 1st Spoke 5 Call for Startup were successfully recruited for the Acceleration phase: **Bbsof** and **Stat4Value**. In line with the collaborative nature of CC1 and for optimal allocation of competencies and resources, **Bbsof** has been supported and coached by the staff allocated to the Accelerator belonging to SPOKE 2, while the latter has been supported and coached by staff belonging to SPOKE 3.

Both companies were actively participating to the program and reported a very positive outcome from the participation, substantially refocusing the value proposition and business mode. It is worth mentioning that **Bbsof** was awarded a Special Prize during the Demo Day of 25th October 2024. Meanwhile, the second cycle of CC1 is now underway. Specifically, the Pre-acceleration phase for this cycle was recently concluded. The second CC1 Selection Day was held on December 3 in Udine. Based on the presentations and outcomes from the Selection Day, the CC1 Committee has admitted three start-up projects stemming from Spoke 5 ecosystem:

AIRFARM (Smart Agri-food and Nutrition), with interconnections spanning **RT1, RT2 and RT3**

EcoBot (Smart Industries) encompassing **RT2 and RT3**

SYNARGY (Health Tech and Services which has a strong focus of the health-related themes coordinated by other spokes (e.g. Spoke 2).

The goal of this next phase is to help these teams in developing a solid business model; their founders will attend the second cycle of the Acceleration program, consisting of 6 workshops and 2 pitch clinics designed to hone their entrepreneurial skills and prepare them for the challenges of scaling their ventures. In parallel, efforts in public communication will ensure that all program milestones will be highlighted. Special focus will be placed on the mission, vision, and innovative aspects of the start-up projects through the production of dedicated content, such as YouTube videos, to showcase their journey and achievements to a broader audience.

5.2. SPOKE 5 CC1 TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES

List of CC1 Tasks:

- CC1.1: Planning and validation
- **CC1.2: Pre-acceleration**
 - Sub Task CC1.2.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (10 Scouting specialists, one for each spoke - two for spoke 5, and pre-acceleration officer) of the pre-acceleration phase.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 9-40
 - Sub Task CC1.2.2: Implementation of the Scouting Stage to attract entrepreneurs-to-be from the university's ecosystems and drive the research effort toward a proof-of-concept.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 10-23
 - Sub Task CC1.2.3: Implementation of the online Entrepreneurial training through Management & Educational Platform to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 12-26
 - Sub Task CC1.2.4: Open innovation activities. The objective of this task is to establish relationships with companies and other partners in order to facilitate the development of new projects, spinoffs, and co-innovation activities between universities, startups, and companies.
Responsible: UNIUD
Duration: months 9-40

- CC1.3: Acceleration
 - Sub Task CC1.3.1: Development of the Key Standardized Elements (Acceleration Framework; Acceleration Physical Spaces) of the acceleration phase to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
Responsible: UNIVR
Duration: months 11-34
 - Sub Task CC1.3.2: Engagement and coordination of the Key Actors (Acceleration officer, 2 StartUp Analysts) of the acceleration phase.
Responsible: UNIVR
Duration: months 14-40
 - Sub Task CC1.3.3: Implementation of the Acceleration phase through Pitch Building & Pitch Session, Selection day, Onboarding and SCUM program. the objective of this phase is to bring the start-ups to validate the market and a scalable business model.
Responsible: UNIVR
Duration: months 15-32

- CC1.4 Fundraising

Task Leader: UniTS
Duration: M15 – M40

Sub Task CC1.4.1: Development of the Fundraising Network and Management. The task involves developing a fundraising network. This may include identifying potential VC capitals/Business Angels, creating fundraising strategies and maintaining the relationships with them. It may also involve using various tools and platforms to manage and track investments, as well as analyze and report on fundraising efforts.

Responsible: UNITS
Duration: months 15-40 Sub

Task CC1.4.2: Implementation of the VC-Invested Stage to support investment-ready scaleups fulfilling their financial needs. This task includes creating a comprehensive business plan that outlines the Start Up's goals, strategies, and financial projections. It should also involve identifying and approaching potential investors, including venture capital firms, and negotiating/structuring investment deals.

Responsible: UNITS

Duration: months 21-34

Sub Task CC1.4.3: Design of the Sustainable Stage. The goal of this task is to provide skills, identify tools and evaluate market strategies to support scale-ups towards their final Exit-IPO or Trade-Sale.

Responsible: UNIPD
Duration: months 23-40

Focus on Task CC1.2: Scouting and Pre-acceleration activities within Spoke 5

Background/State of the Art: For Task CC1.2, several UniPD offices have been contacted to support Spoke 5 activities:

- **Third Mission and Research Valorisation Office:** the office in charge of Third Mission Sector and of all the initial services and support activities to those who intend to start a university spin-off startup and guides them through all the stages of establishment or recognition of the spin-off.
- UniPD Patent and Grant Offices
- **StartCube:** the university incubator of Padua, a structure created to facilitate the birth of new businesses

Technology and knowledge transfer are considered crucial and strategic activities, and concrete and structured actions are taken systemically to promote innovation, valorize internal research and talents, and improve the impact of research results on society and the productive and economic ecosystem. The activities of CC1 have been carried out to align and integrate as much as possible with existing initiatives within Spoke 5.

For what concerns **Sub-task CC1.2.1**, the following profiles were engaged to work on Spoke 5 initiatives within CC1:

- Pier Luigi Franceschini, who covered the role of Scouting Specialist for Spoke 5.
- Alessio Cuccu, who covered the role of Scouting Specialist for Spoke 5.

As for **Sub-task CC1.2.2**, the implementation of the Scouting Stage has consisted of disseminating with UniPd the activities .

For Spoke 5, an open call modality for Pre-seed Startups was implemented and carried out by the Scouting Specialist, aligning with the communication toolkit provided by the Scouting Officer and the Assistant Scouting Officers. The continuous, open call was

- The 1st Call for Start-up Pre-seed was opened in December 2023 and closed in February 2024;
- The 2nd Call for Start-up Pre-seed was opened in June 2024 and closed in September 2024.

In parallel an active campaign of 1:1 contacts with students, researchers and university professors was undertaken to spread the new about the upcoming program and recruit ideas/spinoffs to the program.

Sub-task CC1.2.3 has been developed by other Spokes and will not be treated here

As for **Sub-task CC1.2.4**, a list of 66 innovative companies from Northeastern Italy has been prepared by the Open Innovation Manager. An Open Innovation Day is scheduled on January 30, 2025, in Padua; the iNEST project will be presented and the selected 66 companies will be given the chance to present their needs and approaches to open innovation.

Methodology: For what concerns **Sub-task CC1.2.2**, all the applications for the two Calls for Start-up Pre-seed were collected in a common database. Potential startupperes were contacted by the Scouting Specialist to organize a series of one-to-one meetings to explore together the potential of innovative

ideas and research results to valorize. Start-up projects were then selected according to the Pre-acceleration funnel, which was designed by the Scouting Specialists and SPOKE5 members of Scientific Committee. The Pre-acceleration funnel consists of the following steps:

1. **Pre-screening.** It is performed by Scouting Specialists.
2. **Screening.** It is performed by Scouting Specialists.
3. **Committee evaluation.** It is performed by the CC1 Committee.
4. **Selection Day.** During the Selection Day, all start-up projects from all Spokes that passed the Committee evaluation are presented to the CC1 Committee (and a possible external jury, in the case of the 2nd cycle). The Committee then selects about 10–15 teams for the Acceleration phase. The Selection Day of the 1st cycle was held at the Iuav University of Venice on March 19, 2024. The Selection Day of the 2nd cycle was held at the University of Udine on December 3, 2024.

Ongoing activities: As for **Sub-task CC1.2.2**, all activities described before are now completed.

Focus on Task CC1.3: Acceleration activities within Spoke 5

Background/State of the Art: **Sub-task CC1.3.1** and **Sub-task CC1.3.2** have been developed by other Spokes and will not be treated hereon.

For what concerns **Sub-task CC1.3.3**, a centralized Acceleration program has been developed for the founders of the selected teams so that they can acquire all the knowledge and skills to build a solid business model. With a holistic approach to innovation that leverages synergies between academic research and the business world, the iNEST Accelerator aims to foster the creation of high-tech start-ups, generate skilled employment, and promote sustainable economic development in Northeastern Italy. Emphasis is placed on the preparation of a pitch, as each Acceleration cycle is closed by the Demo Day, a public event where start-up projects are presented to potential investors and professionals, offering significant networking opportunities and potential business collaborations. Start-up projects are evaluated by an external jury, and the most deserving teams are given an award.

Methodology: For **Sub-task CC1.3.3**, the Acceleration program has been structured with a series of in-person workshops, held by professionals involved in Cross-Cutting Activity 1 across the whole Triveneto region, which blend theory and practice in innovation and entrepreneurship. Pitch clinics, in which teams have the opportunity to try their pitch in front of a jury (either internal or external), are also part of the program. In the following, each of the two programs is detailed.

- 1st cycle:
 - Workshop #1: April 19–20, 2024, in Trieste (UniTS): “Strategy innovation and problem-client fit”.
 - Workshop #2: May 10–11, 2024, in Padua: “Solution and market fit”.
 - Workshop #3: May 31–June 1, 2024, in Trento: “Profit model” and a pitch session test.
 - Workshop #4: June 28–29, 2024, in Trieste (SISSA): “Go to market strategy”.
 - Workshop #5: August 30–31, 2024, in Verona: “Funding strategy”.
 - Pitch Clinic: September 20, 2024, in Venice.

- 2nd cycle:
 - Workshop #1: January 17–18, 2025, in Trento: “Introduction and presentation of the strategic plan”.
 - Workshop #2: February 7–8, 2025, in Verona: “Problem, current solutions, and proposition”.
 - Workshop #3: February 28–March 1, 2025, in Udine: “Market and competition”.
 - Workshop #4: March 14–15, 2025, in Venice (Ca’ Foscari): “Governance, vision, mission, and strategy; Business Model”.
 - Pitch Clinic #1: April 4, 2025, in Venice (Iuav).
 - Workshop #5: May 9–10, 2025, in Bolzano: “Action plan & eco-fin plan”.
 - Workshop #6: May 23–24, 2025, in Trieste: “Eco-fin plan & funding”.
 - Pitch Clinic #2: June 6, 2025, in Verona.

Workshops are based on the lean startup methodology, which enables teams to test and adjust their hypotheses about solutions and markets quickly. This approach is particularly effective for technologies emerging from research, which require a clear and flexible commercialization path. Another essential component of the program is peer learning—participants learn from one another by sharing experiences, challenges, and solutions, accelerating their start-up's development. Every start-up team is assigned two coaches, professionals from affiliated universities and institutions who help them apply what learned in workshops to their specific start-up contexts. Coaches follow start-up teams during the workshops and can also organize one-on-one coaching sessions. The 1st cycle of the program also included five webinars, held by mentors—professionals from specific sectors who help all teams in a single field:

- Webinar #1: Presentation of psychological profiles (June 19, 2024) by Beniamino Mirisola;
- Webinar #2: Marketing, customer acquisition, sales (June 24, 2024) by Giacomo Tesolin;
- Webinar #3: IP strategy (July 5, 2024) by Elisa Toniolo;
- Webinar #4: Establishment of an innovative S.r.l. between civil and tax regulations (September 13, 2024) by Valter Carturo;
- Webinar #5: Innovative start-ups and contractual frameworks (September 27, 2024) by Paolo Guaragnella and Giorgio Abbadessa.

The 1st cycle of the activity was concluded by a Demo Day, held in Verona on October 25, 2024. A jury of 7 investors was featured: Augusto Coppola from Cloud Accelerator, Alvise Bonivento from Indaco Venture Partners Sgr, Arianna Tibuzzi from Obloo Ventures, Michele Marcaccio from FNDX to represent Gellify, Tommaso Maschera from Plug and Play, Alessandro Nitti from CIV (Compagnia per l'Innovazione e i Valori), and Enrico Fili from CDP Venture Capital SGR.

Ongoing activities: As for **Sub-task CC1.3.3**, Pier Luigi Franceschini was involved as a coach of 3 teams within the accelerator programme, namely for the team **Discovera** (tools for computational drug design), **Sindrel** (system for drug-delivery) and **Fep** (pathogens detection and prediction, coached in collaboration with David Tacconi and Davide Ederle). The coaching activity consisted in: 1. side-by-side assistance during the Acceleration workshops 2. About 20 online 1:1 meeting carried out with the startups to check the progress of the work done. One meeting with an industrial partner and potential investor was facilitated, as well as a meeting with a potential client for FEP. Coaching calls were also carried out to discuss the possibility to access European funding through the EIC. Pier Luigi has also been contacted to coach the companies within the second cycle.

Focus on Task CC1.4: Acceleration activities within Spoke 5

SPOKE 5 is in charge of the Sub Task CC1.4.3: Design of the Sustainable Stage, in which the main goal is to provide skills, identify tools and evaluate market strategies to support startups and scale-ups towards their final Exit-IPO or Trade-Sale.

CC1.4.3 targets the final phase, preparing scale-ups for a successful exit through either an IPO or acquisition.

At this stage, the scouting specialists have conducted research and identified a range of tools and methodologies developed by both academic institutions and industry practitioners.

Discussions are also underway to offer tailored support, with a primary focus on legal matters related to the exit phase, to each start-up admitted to the Fundraising stage. All findings and proposed actions will be shared and collaboratively reviewed with UNITS SPOKE 8, the lead entity for Task CC1.4.

5.3. SPOKE 5 CC1 DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES

Focus on Task CC1.2: Scouting and Pre-acceleration activities within Spoke 5

For what concerns **Sub-task CC1.2.2**, to promote the application to the two Spoke 5 Calls for Start-up Pre-seed among doctoral students and researchers, two main activities have been led by the Scouting Specialists:

- Research for patents on UniPD database, linked to the main topics of the SPOKE 5 (June-July 2024)
- Start Cup and Contamination Lab collaboration (June-September 2024)
- UniPD partner network contacts (i.e. t2i) (July – September)
- Newsletter to Spin-off and PhD students. (July – August 2024)

Research for patents on UniPD database, linked to the main topics of the SPOKE 5 (June-July 2024)

Following the request emerged on one of the first meeting of kick-off of the second cycle of pre-acceleration (May-June 2024) together with all the other Spokes, Spoke 5 conducted a specific research on patents to check and prove a methodology useful to identify the relevant and best promising patent available in University, with the idea to open specific and focused contact with the patents owners asking to participate to the iNEST Program.

The results will be shown in the next section.

Start Cup and Contamination Lab collaboration (June-September 2024)

UniPD is already well structured in terms of promoting technology transfer and entrepreneurship through its students and PhD graduates. Two main events/activities helped to focus the pre-selection on promising young-new spin-off, start-ups or simple new ideas presented by team selected for StartCup Padova competition or Contamination Lab workshops program.

The results will be shown in the next section.

UniPD partner network contacts (i.e. t2i) (July – September)

UniPD has a huge network of collaborations around the Veneto Region, in particular covering areas as Treviso and Rovigo which don't have their own University. The SPOKE 5 Scouting Specialists had some calls together with New Business Development Manager and Incubator Manager to inform about the possibility to get access to the iNEST programme and to be sure all interesting and relevant idea, start-up and spin-off somehow linked to the University network have been informed to participate to the call.

The results will be shown in the next section.

Newsletter to PhD students. (July – August 2024)

Thanks to the cooperation with the “**SPIN-OFF Università degli Studi di Padova - Settore Qualità della Terza Missione e fondi strutturali**” the SPOKE 5 Scouting Specialists have been able to promote the iNEST Programme on the specific newsletter of the University for Spin-offs and doctorate students, reaching 62 spin-off and 156 total recipients.

5.4. SPOKE 5 CCI MAIN RESULTS

For what concerns **Sub-task CCI.2.2**, the Scouting Specialists were able to open and manage **28 leads** of spinoff/idea holders, **15** applications were registered in the 1st Spoke 5 pre-selection and have been supported and coached by the scouting specialists for taking a decision about their participating to the final stage of the pre-selection. **6** applications were finally accepted and registered in the 2nd and final Spoke 5 pre-selection stage.

These numbers were achieved mainly through frequent updates and meetings between the Scouting Specialists and the idea/spin-off candidates, followed by feedback exchanges between Scouting Specialists and SPOKE 5 Committee.

Pre-acceleration funnel, ideas were then selected:

1. **Pre-screening.** In the 1st cycle, out of 33 entrepreneurial ideas identified for the Spoke 5 Call for Pre-seed Startup, **5 ideas** were admitted to the next selection step.
In the 2nd cycle, out of **15+** applications, **6** ideas were admitted to the next selection step.
2. **Screening.** In the 1st cycle, out of **18** ideas from Spoke 5, **13** projects were admitted to the next selection step.
In the 2nd cycle, out of 6 ideas from Spoke 5, **6** projects were admitted to the next selection step.
3. **Committee evaluation.**
In the 1st cycle, out of **13 projects** from Spoke 5, **5** were admitted to the next selection step.
In the 2nd cycle, out of **6** projects from Spoke 5, **6** were admitted to the next selection step.
4. **Selection Day.** Out of **6** projects from Spoke 5, **2** have been admitted to the 1st Acceleration program, joining 13 teams from other Spokes.
Out of **6** projects from Spoke 5, **3** have been admitted to the 2nd Acceleration program, joining 13 teams from other Spokes.

As for **Sub-task CC1.3.3**, 15 start-up teams participated in the 1st cycle of the program, and 11 have presented their pitch during the Demo Day, including both teams from Spoke 5. **Bbsoft** was awarded with a special prize, whereas **Stat4Value** was not classified. For the 2nd cycle of the program, 3 Spoke 5 teams will be present: **AirFarm, Synargy, EcoBot**.

5.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN

Pre-Acceleration – Task CC1.2

The primary challenge was related to conducting an effective selection of the most promising ideas. The difficulty stemmed from the significant size of the University of Padua (UniPD) and the extensive volume of research output and patents available, making it complex to identify and prioritize high-potential projects. To address this issue, a collaborative approach was adopted. Feedback and insights were sought from various teams and offices within UniPD and its broader network, including Third Mission, Technology Transfer, and Research Valorisation units. This multi-layered selection process aimed to ensure that a diverse evaluation framework would yield the best final choices of ideas, projects, and spin-offs for participation in the iNEST Acceleration Program.

Timelines and Commitment

The rigid and precise timelines imposed by the program posed a barrier for some promising startup ideas that required greater flexibility. Participants perceived this flexibility as necessary to better manage ongoing projects alongside their involvement in the iNEST program. For certain candidates, the lack of adaptable scheduling and the requirement for a fixed level of availability hindered their participation, preventing them from progressing beyond the pre-selection stage.

Status of Spin-offs and Startups

Another issue involved understanding the organizational structure and independence of startups. In some cases, despite an initial expression of interest, it became evident that the process might lead to unmet expectations for certain teams. This highlighted the need for clearer communication and alignment regarding the goals and requirements of the acceleration process.

Need for Support for Professors and Doctoral Students

Professors and doctoral students often expressed reluctance to engage with the economic and financial aspects of their projects. Addressing this concern could benefit from the development of targeted initiatives, such as workshops or networking events that connect patent holders with local businesses. These events would foster partnerships, providing practical guidance and facilitating the commercial application of research.

Additionally, observing the diverse levels of capability among teams in managing and capitalizing on patents suggests an opportunity to organize dedicated sessions for idea exchange. These could involve UniPD teams holding valuable patents, enabling them to share experiences, brainstorm innovative methods, and collaborate on strategies for enhancing the value and impact of their intellectual property.

ACCELERATION - Task CC1.3

Startups at different level of maturity were admitted to the accelerator programme, which implied the programme to adopt a rather flexible approach. Also startups with different business models were engaged: on the one hand this favoured cross-fertilisation, on the other hand it made it difficult to provide an homogeneous support. The type and approach of the coaches and mentors was the means through which this flexible approach was implemented.

5.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES

With the beginning of the Fundraising phase, corresponding to **Task CC1.4**, the start-up projects of the 1st cycle are now meeting potential investors. On November 18, 2024, both Spoke 5 teams participated in a meeting with a Business Angel; on January 8, SINDREL was also involved in a meeting for the preparation of useful documentation and other tips. Valorizing these ideas and growing the business will be the main upcoming challenge for these start-up projects.

For the 2nd cycle of Cross-Cutting Activity 1, the main challenge will be to improve the Acceleration program and replicate what was successful in the 1st cycle. By establishing a new standard in acceleration and incubation programs, iNEST can become a reference for innovation among other incubators from Triveneto and Italy as a whole.

6. SPOKE 6 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the Cross-Cutting Activity 1

Spoke 6 research focuses on enabling businesses in tourism, culture, and creative sectors to transform research into practical outcomes via prototypes, experiments, and innovations. Its incubation and acceleration projects support entrepreneurial ideas in these fields, guided by four key Research Topics (RTs), namely:

- **RT 1 - New Digital Technologies**

These lines promote the development of innovative projects that combine knowledge of the tourism and cultural domain with the adoption of new digital technologies. These include artificial intelligence, blockchain and NFT, IoT and mobile sensing, virtual and augmented reality, which will serve as a reference for projects to be implemented in the following macro-environments;

- **RT 2 - Data analysis**

These converge on the analysis of big data in tourism and culture from heterogeneous sources. The aim is thus to develop tools to support public policies and more sustainable destination management & marketing strategies. The lines of research may take the form of projects to be implemented in different fields;

- **RT 3 - Sustainable business models**

RT3 research lines aim at transforming the business models of tourism, cultural and creative enterprises, organisations and ecosystems into sustainable ones.

- **RT 4 - New narratives and communication strategies**

The RT4 research lines aim to develop new narrative tools to overcome the stereotypes of tourist destinations and to reconfigure communication in terms of inclusiveness and sustainability.

Spoke 6, led by Ca' Foscari University with partners from the Universities of Verona, Trento, and Bolzano, is establishing a robust tourism ecosystem that integrates culture, creativity, and advanced digital and data analysis technologies. It focuses on four key research areas to explore the intricate connections within the tourism sector, fostering innovation, sustainability, and transformative practices.

Within the framework of the iNEST project, Cross-Cutting Activity 1 plays an important role in fostering a coordinated and transversal approach across all Spokes within the iNEST project. Aligned with the framework of an innovation ecosystem, this activity serves the purpose of valorizing innovative ideas arising from the research activities of Spoke 6 and facilitating the generation and development of research start-ups and spin-offs. Furthermore, it assumes a fundamental role in coordinating and stimulating the achievement of project objectives, promoting the exploration of new solutions and pathways through continuous listening and exchange. This approach creates a vital communication system essential for fostering growth and innovation across the entire ecosystem.

6.1. SPOKE 6 CCI OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW

Cross-Cutting Activity 1 aims to foster the creation and selection of innovative ideas generated by the scientific work of Spoke 6, guiding them towards their transformation into research-driven start-ups and spin-offs. To achieve this, CCI is structured into four distinct phases.

The initial phase focuses on the planning and validation of activities, which includes recruiting specialized personnel to support the implementation of initiatives as outlined by the CCI committee.

The first cycle of CCI has successfully concluded with positive outcomes. The selected start-up [H4UNI](#) has demonstrated significant growth and progress, including establishing a key partnership to facilitate market entry. Currently, the platform is fully operational and actively entering the market, marking an important milestone in its development. Nicola Baldan

The 2nd cycle of CCI is now officially underway, with the pre-acceleration phase recently completed. On 3 December, the 2nd Selection Day took place in Udine, where the CCI Committee evaluated the participating projects. As a result, two start-ups from Spoke 6, [Algae Scope](#) and [Fenix Ceramics](#), were selected to move forward, while **Alba** - the third startup present on the Selection Day - was not accepted.

The next phase aims to help these start-ups develop robust business models. Their founders will take part in a comprehensive acceleration programme, including six workshops and two pitch clinics, designed to enhance their entrepreneurial skills and prepare them to scale their ventures.

At the same time, public communication efforts will focus on highlighting key milestones of the programme. Particular emphasis will be placed on showcasing the mission, vision and innovative aspects of the start-ups. This will be achieved through the production of dedicated content, such as YouTube videos, to share their progress and achievements with a wider audience.

6.2. SPOKE 6 CCI TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES

List of CCI Tasks:

- CCI.1: Planning and validation
- **CCI.2: Pre-acceleration**

Sub Task CCI.2.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (10 Scouting specialists, one for each spoke - two for spoke 5, and pre-acceleration officer) of the pre-acceleration phase. Responsible: UNIVE - Duration: months 9-40

Sub Task CCI.2.2: Implementation of the Scouting Stage to attract entrepreneurs-to-be from the university's ecosystems and drive the research effort toward a proof-of-concept. Responsible: UNIVE - Duration: months 10-23

Sub Task CCI.2.3: Implementation of the online Entrepreneurial training through Management & Educational Platform to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem. Responsible: UNIVE - Duration: months 12-26

Sub Task CC1.2.4: Open innovation activities. The objective of this task is to establish relationships with companies and other partners in order to facilitate the development of new projects, spinoffs, and co-innovation activities between universities, startups, and companies. Responsible: UNIUD - Duration: months 9-40

- CC1.3: Acceleration

Sub Task CC1.3.1: Development of the Key Standardized Elements (Acceleration Framework; Acceleration Physical Spaces) of the acceleration phase to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem. Responsible: UNIVR - Duration: months 11-34

Sub Task CC1.3.2: Engagement and coordination of the Key Actors (Acceleration officer, 2 StartUp Analysts) of the acceleration phase. Responsible: UNIVR - Duration: months 14-40

Sub Task CC1.3.3: Implementation of the Acceleration phase through Pitch Building & Pitch Session, Selection day, Onboarding and SCRUM program. The objective of this phase is to bring the start-ups to validate the market and a scalable business model. Responsible: UNIVR - Duration: months 15-32

- CC1.4: Fundraising

Focus on Task CC1.2: Scouting and Pre-acceleration activities within Spoke 6

Background/State of the Art:

For task CC1, as in the first cycle, the following existing startup support initiatives were involved:

- **CLab** (Ca' Foscari Laboratori di Didattica Attiva): provides hands-on educational experiences in collaboration with external partners.
- **PinK** (Promozione dell'Innovazione e del Know-how): facilitates innovation and knowledge transfer between university research and the local community.
- **Student Associations:** play a pivotal role in fostering a vibrant academic and social environment.

In the second cycle, activities expanded to include direct engagement of the eight departments within Ca' Foscari University. This involved contacting department directors, third mission representatives, and professors leading research groups. These interactions are considered crucial and strategic, with concrete and structured actions systematically taken to: promote innovation, valorize internal research and talents, enhance the societal, productive, and economic impact of research results. For Sub-task CC1.2.1, the initiatives related to Spoke 6 within CC1 were led by Viviana Carlet, Scouting Specialist.

Key success factors for startups, as identified through literature and best practices, include collaborative networks, access to funding, mentorship, and robust infrastructure.

These findings offer a comprehensive understanding of Ca' Foscari's startup ecosystem, leveraging internal resources and global innovation trends to inform and guide Spoke 6 initiatives.

The implementation of the Scouting Stage has consisted of preparing a Call for Start-up Pre-seed, one for each Spoke and each cycle of the activity. For Spoke 6, two Calls for Start-up Pre-seed were prepared by the Scouting Specialist, under the supervision of the Scouting Officer and the Assistant Scouting Officers:

- The 1st Call for Start-up Pre-seed was opened in December 2023 and closed in February 2024;
- The 2nd Call for Start-up Pre-seed was opened in March 2024 and closed in September 2024.

Methodology: All the applications for the two Calls for Start-up Pre-seed were collected in a common database. Potential start-uppers were contacted by the Scouting Specialist to organise a series of one-to-one meetings to explore together the potential of innovative ideas and research results to valorize. Start-up projects were then selected according to the Pre-acceleration funnel, which was designed by the Scouting Officer and his Assistants. The Pre-acceleration funnel consists of the following steps:

1. Pre-screening. It is performed by Scouting Specialists.
2. Screening. It is performed by Scouting Specialists.
3. Committee evaluation. It is performed by the CCI Committee.
4. Selection Day. During the Selection Day, all start-up projects from all Spokes that passed the Committee evaluation are presented to the CCI Committee (and a possible external jury, in the case of the 2nd cycle). The Committee then selects about 10–15 teams for the Acceleration phase. The Selection Day of the 1st cycle was held at the Iuav University of Venice on March 19, 2024. The Selection Day of the 2nd cycle was held at the University of Udine on December 3, 2024.

Focus on Task CCI.3: Acceleration activities within Spoke 6

Background/State of the Art: a centralized Acceleration program has been developed for the founders of the selected teams so that they can acquire all the knowledge and skills to build a solid business model. With a holistic approach to innovation that leverages synergies between academic research and the business world, the iNEST Accelerator aims to foster the creation of high-tech start-ups, generate skilled employment, and promote sustainable economic development in Northeastern Italy. Particular emphasis is placed on the preparation of a pitch, as each Acceleration cycle is closed by the Demo Day, a public event where start-up projects are presented to potential investors and professionals, offering significant networking opportunities and potential business collaborations. Start-up projects are evaluated by an external jury, and the most deserving teams are given an award. The Spoke 6 Scouting Specialist will be actively involved in all stages of the process and will remain available throughout. In particular, they will provide dedicated support and mentoring to two start-ups: **EcoBot** and **OptiLink**.

Methodology: the Acceleration program has been structured with a series of in-person workshops, held by professionals involved in Cross-Cutting Activity 1 across the whole Triveneto region, which blend theory and practice in innovation and entrepreneurship. Pitch clinics, in which teams have the opportunity to try their pitch in front of a jury (either internal or external), are also part of the program. In the following, each of the two programs is detailed.

- 1st cycle:
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- Pitch Clinic: September 20, 2024, in Venice.
- 2nd cycle:
 - Workshop #1: January 17–18, 2025, in Trento: “Introduction and presentation of the strategic plan”.
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 - Workshop #4: March 14–15, 2025, in Venice (Ca’ Foscari): “Governance, vision, mission, and strategy; Business Model”.
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 - Pitch Clinic #2: June 6, 2025, in Verona.

Workshops are based on the lean startup methodology, which enables teams to test and adjust their hypotheses about solutions and markets quickly. This approach is particularly effective for technologies emerging from research, which require a clear and flexible commercialization path. Another essential component of the program is peer learning—participants learn from one another by sharing experiences, challenges, and solutions, accelerating their start-up's development. Every start-up team is assigned two coaches, professionals from affiliated universities and institutions who help them apply what learned in workshops to their specific start-up contexts. Coaches follow start-up teams during the workshops and can also organize one-on-one coaching sessions. The 1st cycle of the program also included five webinars, held by mentors—professionals from specific sectors who help all teams in a single field:

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- Webinar #3: IP strategy (July 5, 2024) by Elisa Toniolo;
- Webinar #4: Establishment of an innovative S.r.l. between civil and tax regulations (September 13, 2024) by Valter Carturo;
- Webinar #5: Innovative start-ups and contractual frameworks (September 27, 2024) by Paolo Guaragnella and Giorgio Abbadessa.

The 1st cycle of the activity was concluded by a Demo Day, held in Verona on October 25, 2024. A jury of 7 investors was featured: Augusto Coppola from Cloud Accelerator, Alvisè Bonivento from Indaco Venture Partners Sgr, Arianna Tibuzzi from Obloo Ventures, Michele Marcaccio from FNDX to represent Gellify, Tommaso Maschera from Plug and Play, Alessandro Nitti from CIV (Compagnia per l'Innovazione e i Valori), and Enrico Fili from CDP Venture Capital SGR.

Ongoing activities: As for **Sub-task CC1.3.3**, the 2nd cycle of the Acceleration program is about to begin. All appointments, apart from the Demo Day, have been scheduled. The AcceleratorApp software is being used for the organization and management of this cycle of the activity.

6.3. SPOKE 6 CCI DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES

Focus on Task CC1.2: Scouting and Pre-acceleration activities within Spoke 6

Sub-task CC1.2.2 - To promote the application to the two Spoke 6 Calls for Start-up Pre-seed among doctoral students and researchers, three events were organized, adopting an ecosystemic approach characteristic of Spoke 6:

- iNEST Cinema Professionals Event, held on July 23, 2024 - Industry days at Lago Film Fest
- iNEST - The future in acceleration: from idea to start-up (event in collaboration with Spoke 4 + Spoke 6), September 26 2024 - Combo, Venice
- iNEST - Turistic and cultural startups meeting, October 14 2024 - 10am 4pm - Ca' Bottacin, Venice

The iNEST scouting effort was launched and supported by three key events aimed at engaging entrepreneurs and fostering project development:

Lago Film Fest - Business Days: Scouting Officer Andrea Marella introduced iNEST to young entrepreneurs in the film industry and highlighted opportunities for creative and cultural projects.

The future in acceleration: in collaboration with Spoke 4 IUAV University, this event presented the iNEST initiative and featured presentations by two start-ups completing their acceleration phase: *H4Uni* (Ca' Foscari) and *ReHub* (IUAV). The session facilitated valuable networking between researchers, students and cultural professionals, at Combo in Venice - informal meeting place.

Tailored support for cultural and tourism projects: Recognising the specific needs of cultural and tourism-focused ideas, a personalised support session was conducted to strengthen these projects and align them with the iNEST framework.

These activities were essential in raising awareness, connecting stakeholders and supporting the development of diverse entrepreneurial ideas. During these events, iNEST and Cross-Cutting Activity 1 were presented by Spoke 6 and CCI representatives, and guidelines for preparing a good pitch were provided.

The launch of the two calls and the promotion of related events were widely disseminated through a number of channels. These included news articles published on the iNEST, Spoke 6 and UNVE websites, social media posts on LinkedIn and Facebook, targeted emails via PINK and CLab, and messages shared in internal student chat groups. All promotional activities were carried out in collaboration with and coordinated by CESA.

Dissemination of the two Selection Days was similarly robust, with articles on the iNEST and Spoke 6 websites and posts on the iNEST LinkedIn and Facebook pages. In addition, the visibility of the first Selection Day was enhanced by a YouTube video and two press releases issued before and after the event, with the support of the press offices of both Ca' Foscari University and IUAV University of Venice.

6.4. SPOKE 6 CCI MAIN RESULTS

The most significant achievements of Spoke 6 CCI have been in the area of communication, where efforts have significantly increased the collection of contacts both within the University and from external sources.

Results of the 1st round: **31 ideas** were identified during the pre-screening phase - 10 applicants completed the selection form - 4 projects were evaluated by the panel - 4 projects were presented at the selection day. Of these, **1 startup advanced to the 1st acceleration programme**. Notably, it was

the only startup focused on social dynamics to successfully reach the Demo Day (all the others dealt with technical or scientific issues rather than social interactions).

Results of the 2nd round, the second call for ideas generated more than 70 contacts of interest- 51 applicants registered, with a notable success in reaching scientific research centres, one of our main objectives; the numbers: **70+** direct contacts made - **51 pre-screening forms completed**, with almost all applicants receiving a face-to-face meeting (of these, 25 were directly linked to Ca' Foscari University: 6 professors, 16 students, 4 researchers, 2 research fellows, 1 doctoral student, 1 student project developed by the Ca' Foscari CLab, 9 selection forms completed) - **4** projects evaluated by the selection committee- **3** projects presented at the selection day - **2 start-ups selected for the 2nd Acceleration Programme**.

Of all the events organised, the **The future in acceleration** event at COMBO was certainly a great success, both in terms of active participation and in terms of initiating a collaboration with Spoke 4. This collaboration led to the realisation of the first initiative for meeting and "exchanging" skills between candidates. Although there is room for improvement, it is worth noting that no other Spoke has undertaken a similar initiative.

This progression demonstrates the successful engagement of the academic and research community, culminating in greater participation and more impactful results in the second round.

6.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN

The main problem was to involve PhD students and researchers, who are typically oriented towards basic research and unaware of entrepreneurial opportunities. This resulted in a limited number of applications in the first phase. For the second cycle, corrective actions included extending the scouting efforts to researchers from other Spoke 6 affiliates and collaborating on procedures and methodologies. The involvement of the scouting officer, professors and the scouting specialist proved crucial in bridging this gap and encouraging participation.

A major difficulty was the mismatch between research ideas - often brilliant and well suited to the development of new businesses - and the entrepreneurial expertise needed to bring these ideas to market. The separation between the research and business worlds posed significant challenges in transforming academic ideas into viable businesses.

Cultural and tourism projects, while rich and innovative, often lacked the entrepreneurial skills to succeed in a market-driven environment. These projects needed additional time and tailored support to realise their potential, even though they were not fully aligned with the acceleration programme. Many of these initiatives require alternative business models that are better suited to their nature.

The scouting phase established basic processes for identifying and supporting innovative ideas in the humanities. Key efforts included: refining selected projects with a focus on problem definition, solutions and the creation of effective business models; emphasising social impact and economic sustainability; providing specific guidance on pitch preparation to ensure clear and effective communication of ideas.

The projects identified were characterised by a strong cultural and inclusive impact, as well as originality and diversity of ideas. However, scalability and long-term economic sustainability remain critical weaknesses. These limitations affect the projects' attractiveness to traditional investors and highlight the need for alternative funding strategies and support systems tailored to the unique characteristics of cultural and humanities-focused initiatives.

6.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES

Looking ahead, the focus will be on:

- Ongoing support and ecosystem building: creating a supportive environment to nurture ideas and encourage humanistic entrepreneurship. This includes creating a network that supports innovation and bridges the gap between creative concepts and market implementation.
- Experimenting with hybrid business models: developing innovative business models that combine profitability with cultural and social impact. These models aim to transcend traditional start-up dynamics, ensuring market relevance while addressing societal and cultural needs.
- Integrating culture, entrepreneurship and innovation: strengthening the synergy between these fields to foster sustainable initiatives. By aligning cultural resources with entrepreneurial strategies and technological advances, the aim is to respond effectively to the evolving needs of communities.
- Building bridges between research and management: creating links between technical and scientific research, cultural ideas and management expertise. These aspects are present within the university but rarely intersect, both physically (as they are often located in different spaces) and conceptually (lack of platforms for open dialogue and interaction). Initiatives such as the collaboration with the IUAV - a university dedicated to artistic creation - are particularly valuable. Such partnerships activate diverse processes, stimulate collaborative creation and encourage the sharing and distribution of competences.

The overall objective is to establish humanistic entrepreneurship as a cornerstone of innovation, capable of generating cultural, economic and social value. This approach seeks to redefine innovation paradigms, promote inclusivity and sustainability, and foster projects that have a meaningful impact on society

Scouting di nuove idee imprenditoriali in materia di turismo, cultura e creatività

Open call

INEST, Spoke 6
Ecosistema Turismo, Cultura e Imprese Creative

Partner leader: Università Ca' Foscari Venezia

Affiliazioni: UNIST, UNIVERSITÀ CA' FOSCARI VENEZIA, UNIVERSITÀ DEL SALENTO, UNIVERSITÀ DEL PIEMONTE, UNIVERSITÀ DEL SUD TIROLI

Open call

Sono aperte le iscrizioni per accelerare nuove idee imprenditoriali sui temi del turismo, cultura e creatività!

Cosa cerchiamo?
All'interno delle Cross-Cutting Activity 1 dell'Ecosistema INEST, si cercano le migliori risorse della ricerca in materia di turismo, cultura e creatività. I fenomeni di turismo e cultura sono collegati in modo imprevedibile. In questi ambiti lo Spoke 6 porta avanti la sua ricerca con quattro research topic: nuove tecnologie digitali, flussi e analisi di dati, nuovi modelli di business e nuove narrazioni e comunicazione per il mondo turistico e culturale. **L'obiettivo della open call è esplorare e ascoltare le idee di chi su questi temi ha qualcosa da dire, anche partendo dal livello zero. Scopri le fasi di accelerazione.**

Chi cerchiamo?
Futuri imprenditori che ora sono studenti, dottorandi, ricercatori, docenti con intuizioni e idee di carattere innovativo per il settore turistico e culturale. Neo-imprenditori con idee chiare e start-up da avviare o già avviate.

Come iscriversi?
Se hai un progetto, un'intuizione o un'idea imprenditoriale che parte da zero, compila questo form di presentazione dedicato alle idee imprenditoriali per nuove start-up.
Scadenza per l'iscrizione: 30 agosto 2024.
<https://forms.gle/kzizozAVg21Qw69>

Se sei una start up innovativa in ambito turistico e cerchi sostegno e finanziamento (cosa dovrebbero fare qui?) compila questo form per la selezione di start-up.
Scadenza per l'iscrizione: 21 ottobre 2024.
<https://forms.gle/hB3s5EHokkdQm3br7>

Per informazioni e supporto all'iscrizione contattare la Scouting Specialist Viviana Carlet all'indirizzo email: viviana.carlet@unive.it

Partner leader: Università Ca' Foscari Venezia

Affiliazioni: UNIST, UNIVERSITÀ CA' FOSCARI VENEZIA, UNIVERSITÀ DEL SALENTO, UNIVERSITÀ DEL PIEMONTE, UNIVERSITÀ DEL SUD TIROLI

Lago Film Fest

SCARICA IL PROGRAMMA IN PDF SITO FESTIVAL COMPRA I BIGLIETTI EDIZIONI

Stories of Other Worlds: iNest, the networked innovation ecosystem

B.I.D. - Barefoot Industry Days

with Andrea Marella | 15' |

martedì 23 luglio 2024, 17:45 @ LOUNGE
Solo in presenza

Biglietti

iNest is an innovation ecosystem that connects universities, research institutions and companies to drive technological advancement and digital transformation in the North-East of Italy. Join us to explore how iNest fosters collaboration and sustainability across diverse sectors such as industry, agriculture and culture.

Andrea Marella, Scouting Officer, will present the CC1 activity led by Ca' Foscari University, which valorises innovative ideas and facilitates the creation and development of research start-ups and spin-offs through pre-acceleration and acceleration processes.

iNEST - Il futuro in accelerazione: dall'idea alla start-up

Martedì 26/09/2024
ore 18:30

Combo
Campo dei Gesuiti, 4878
Venezia

Programma

18:30 Accoglienza e registrazione	19:40 Presentazione di nuove idee di startup
19:00 Presentazione del programma di accelerazione iNEST - CC1 con <i>Andrea Marella</i>	20:00 Storia di una startup di successo
19:15 <i>Davide Tiso</i> intervista progetti selezionati per l'edizione 2023/2024: • rehub, Università Iuav di Venezia • N4uni, Università Ca' Foscari Venezia	20:15 Networking

Per ulteriori informazioni

CC1 Consorzio di Competenze e Competenze

References

We report here the list of the links to the webpages relevant to Spoke 6 and in particular to Cross-Cutting Activity 1:

- [Spoke 6 website](#)
- [Cross-Cutting Activity 1 page on the iNEST website](#)
- [Cross-Cutting Activity 1 page on the Spoke 6 website](#)
- [Results of the 1st cycle of CC1 \(page on the iNEST website\)](#)
- [List of news concerning CC1 on the iNEST website](#)

7.SPOKE 7 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the Cross-Cutting Activity 1

The research activities of Spoke 7 address current issues in the sector of smart agri-food. These are supported and enhanced by four Research Topics (RTs), namely:

- **RT1** - Business models for a sustainable agri-food
- **RT2** - Process and product innovation for a sustainable agri-food
- **RT3** - Circular economy
- **RT4** - Logistics, supply chain and vertical coordination

In this scientific context, Cross-Cutting Activity 1 plays an important role in fostering a coordinated and transversal approach across all Spokes within the iNEST project. Aligned with the framework of an innovation ecosystem, this activity serves the purpose of valorizing innovative ideas arising from the research activities of Spoke 7 and facilitating the generation and development of research start-ups and spin-offs.

7.1. SPOKE 7 CCI OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW

The research activities of Spoke7 are focused on advancing research and facilitating technology transfer within the field of smart agri-food. The convergence of digital and green transformations necessitates a comprehensive strategy for agri-food systems, wherein intelligent solutions are cultivated across various domains such as business administration, production (including primary production and industrial processing), circular economy, logistics, and supply chain management. Multiple food value chains within the Nord-Est territory (including grape and wine, olive oil, dairy, baked goods, crops, food and feed, fisheries, and aquaculture) will be addressed through diverse dimensions of potential digital and green innovations. These aims are supported and enhanced by four Research Topics (RTs), namely:

- RT1 Business models for sustainable agri-food at different levels, these activities will focus on the analysis of sustainable business models and sustainability performance in agri-food businesses and of consumer response to corporate social responsibility practices. Through a twin transition on agri-food business models and value chains, the output will be the elaboration of diagnostic and analytic tools to measure gaps and identify transitions in business models at the firm and value chain level.
- RT2 Process/product innovation for sustainable agri-food. The activities will be focused on the Development of innovative systems, based on real time processing of sensor data using process-based, AI and data-driven approaches, for improving crop and food production processes, finished products quality, and packaging. This will exploit also the use of extracts, bio-resources, bio-molecules and digital databases for development of innovative processes and products.
- RT3 Circular economy, where the goals will be that of developing novel foods, feeds, and ingredients derived from agricultural by-products through efficient recovery processes; conducting life cycle assessments (LCA) and devise tools and technologies for assessing nutritional value, and, finally, evaluating the economic viability and market appeal of utilizing by-products, incorporating consumer perception studies.
- RT4 Logistics, supply chain and vertical coordination with the aim of analyzing the sustainability and circular economy practices in agri-food firms across the supply chain and develop suitable data management platforms. Moreover, there will be focus on developing novel technologies for

sustainable supply chain through management, integration, transparency, and authenticity of large amount of heterogenous data.,

7.2. SPOKE 7 CC1 TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES

Pre-acceleration

Starting just before the end of the year 2023, when the specialists Franco Bocchini, Gianni Tortella, and Valter Carturo were involved in the iNEST project, a strong scouting activity was conducted to find out ideas from researchers and students, using “Call for Ideas” forms, Academic Departments’ suggestions, evaluation of patents, meetings with existing and planned spinoffs, both for the first round with the deadline on the end of March and the second round with the deadline on the end of November.

Full availability to evaluate the readiness of every project has been granted, with large professional support for the initial development of all the proposed projects that really aimed to reach the market and had a reasonable possibility.

After the end of these activities, however, ideas that have already been examined and new ones that aim to become spinoffs remain under observation.

Acceleration

Meanwhile, the first acceleration program, **which spoke 7 helped manage with various activities of its specialists (also through participation in the various sprints in Trieste, Udine, Verona and Venice)**, started for the startups selected by the jury and run through all the spokes involved had a final act in Verona in front of possible investors hopefully interested in supporting some teams. The second acceleration program, concerning the newly selected projects, started in Trento on January 17 and 18, 2025 with the first sprint. The following sprints will be on February 7/8 in Verona, February 28 and March 1 in Udine, March 14 and 15 in Venice, April 4 in Venice (1st cut off), May 9 and 10 in Bolzano, May 23 and 24 in Trieste and June 6 in Verona (2nd cut off).

7.3. SPOKE 7 CC1 DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES

Following the “handshake meeting” in Venice, held on December 13th, 2023 - the first involving UniVR experts - the collaboration with UniVE with the role of coordinator for this scouting and pre-acceleration phase and the whole iNEST structure has been usefully ongoing.

The technical staff of the Liaison Office, represented by Simone Sprea and Valentina Nicolini together with Maria Gabaldo, (Research Area Manager of UniVR) was efficient in launching two “calls for ideas”, effective in establishing contacts with professors and researchers, and very useful also discussing patents and spinoffs.

7.4. SPOKE 7 CC1 MAIN RESULTS

Both for the first and the second round, UniVR brought four very interesting projects in front of the jury, two of them passed the selection and were admitted to the acceleration program.

Even if there is moderate satisfaction with this result, the feeling is that in the first round the selection by the jury seemed to be too academic: the second one gave the impression of being better focused on the right criteria due to the different composition with the involvement of professional investors.

It has to be said that the two excluded UniVR projects (AQUISIO and COOL DATA), even if good, deserved their failure providing a poor pitch presentation: the reason was the lack of specific training, refusing to accept the specialists' support offer even if it was suggested more than one time.

In any case, the main result is a general increase in awareness regarding the connection between research and the market.

7.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN

A problem remains the lack of fascination for the already structured spin-offs, unable to understand what advantage they could get, without a "real money" injection: to overcome this, the main answer regards the wideness of the relationships in the system, able to open more doors than at present.

A not secondary one is the insufficient attention given by the researchers to such programs, which could be intensified and better communicated inside the Universities, trying to involve economic actors too.

A third one, as shown by this experience with some ideas that did not pass the final selection, is the difficulty of convincing founders coming from the research environment that also the communication – a pitch is communication - is important, not only the scientific quality of their idea.

A fourth one is the average quality of ideas by students, often too vague and ingenuous, who need to be specifically trained to develop their intuitions into effective projects.

7.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES

On January 29, 2025, a meeting in Venice will be focused on discussing potential activities which could be held after the end of iNEST. In addition, we will set up a UNIVR internal course for technology transfer. The course will be designed for young researchers who are interested in technology transfer. The aim will be to form operative coaches that could be employed in the next future to continue the technology transfer initiated that has started with iNEST.

8. SPOKE 8 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the Cross-Cutting Activity 1

The research activities of Spoke 8 address current issues in the sectors of maritime, marine and inland water technologies: towards the digital twin of the Upper Adriatic. These are supported and enhanced by five Research Topics (RTs), namely:

- **RT1** Biology of hydrosphere ecosystems
- **RT2** Physical-chemical risks and impacts on the hydrosphere
- **RT3** Sustainable waterway mobility
- **RT4** Land-sea integrated maritime and spatial Planning
- **RT5** North Adriatic Digital twin

In this scientific context, the **Cross-Cutting Activity 1** plays an important role in fostering a coordinated and transversal approach across all Spokes within the iNEST project. Aligned with the framework of an innovation ecosystem, this activity serves the purpose of valorizing innovative ideas arising from the research activities of the Spoke 8 and facilitating the generation and development of research start-ups and spin-offs.

8.1. SPOKE 8 CC1 OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW

Within the iNEST Consortium, the overarching goal of the CC1 is to foster the generation and selection of innovative ideas emerging from the scientific activities of Spoke 8, with the ultimate aim of transforming these ideas into research-based start-ups and spin-offs. To achieve this, CC1 is structured into four distinct phases.

The first phase focuses on the planning and validation of activities, involving university personnel and industry technical personnel dedicated to supporting the initiatives as outlined by the CC1 Committee.

The first cycle of CC1 completed in October 2024 with the Demo Day and the starting of the Fundraising phase. Although two start-up projects were initially selected through the first Spoke 8 Call for Start-up, unfortunately, none advanced to the final stages of development as start-ups or spin-offs. Meanwhile, the second cycle of CC1 has officially begun. As in the first cycle, the pre-acceleration and scouting activities were intended to collect entrepreneurial ideas, select them and provide the most promising ones with the basic tools for the development and flourishing of their innovative potential, thus allowing them to turn into start-ups and spin-offs. Differently from the first cycle, where we involved as a wide public as possible to raise participants' awareness on the key concepts of innovation and entrepreneurship, in the second cycle a pre-selection of the ideas has been carried out, in order to let only high-quality ideas with real potential for funding apply for the Call for Start-up. The Scouting phase for the second cycle has concluded, culminating in the second Selection Day of CC1, held on December 3 in Udine. During this event, the CC1 Committee approved two start-up projects linked to Spoke 8:

- **OptiLink:** This project tackles inefficiencies and resource constraints in the healthcare system through two AI-driven solutions:
 - *VisionDOC*, a vision system designed to enhance early diagnosis and medical image analysis;

- o *ChatDOC*, a tool that supports doctors in pharmaceutical prescriptions, optimizing both treatment costs and effectiveness.
- **SIPEOM**: Developed by the UniTS DIA Department, this project introduces *Probabilistic Emissions Forecast*, an advanced forecasting system that integrates cutting-edge simulations to predict fuel consumption and greenhouse gas emissions in maritime operations more accurately. This aims at promoting sustainable practices and regulatory compliance in the sector.

The next phase aims to assist these teams in developing robust business models. To this end, the founders will join a new Acceleration Program comprising six workshops and two pitch clinics, designed to refine their entrepreneurial skills and prepare them for scaling their ventures. Concurrently, public communication initiatives will ensure that the program's milestones are effectively showcased. Emphasis will be placed on highlighting the mission, vision, and innovative aspects of the start-up projects through dedicated content, such as YouTube videos, to share their journey and achievements with a broader audience.

8.2. SPOKE 8 CCI TASKS AND ONGOING ACTIVITIES

List of CCI Tasks:

- CCI.1: Planning and validation
- CCI.2: Pre-acceleration
 - Sub Task CCI.2.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (10 Scouting specialists, one for each spoke - two for spoke 5, and pre-acceleration officer) of the pre-acceleration phase.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 9-40
 - Sub Task CCI.2.2: Implementation of the Scouting Stage to attract entrepreneurs-to-be from the university's ecosystems and drive the research effort toward a proof-of-concept.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 10-23
 - Sub Task CCI.2.3: Implementation of the online Entrepreneurial training through Management & Educational Platform to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 12-26
 - Sub Task CCI.2.4: Open innovation activities. The objective of this task is to establish relationships with companies and other partners in order to facilitate the development of new projects, spinoffs, and co-innovation activities between universities, startups, and companies.

Responsible: UNIUD
Duration: months 9-40

- CC1.3: Acceleration
 - Sub Task CC1.3.1: Development of the Key Standardized Elements (Acceleration Framework; Acceleration Physical Spaces) of the acceleration phase to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
Responsible: UNIVR
Duration: months 11-34
 - Sub Task CC1.3.2: Engagement and coordination of the Key Actors (Acceleration officer, 2 StartUp Analysts) of the acceleration phase.
Responsible: UNIVR
Duration: months 14-40
 - Sub Task CC1.3.3: Implementation of the Acceleration phase through Pitch Building & Pitch Session, Selection day, Onboarding and SCUM program. The objective of this phase is to bring the start-ups to validate the market and a scalable business model.
Responsible: UNIVR
Duration: months 15-32
- CC1.4: Fundraising

Focus on Task CC1.2: Scouting and Pre-acceleration activities within Spoke 8

Background/State of the Art: For **subtask CC1.2.1**, our scouting specialists (Tiziana Perin and Salvatore Dore) continued the planned activities of the first cycle of CCI, leading the selected start-ups for Spoke 8 to the Demo Day in Verona. They also contributed to craft the activities of the second cycle.

Sub-task CC1.2.2 for the first cycle has been extensively described in the previous annual report. As for the second cycle, POLOAA and UniTS shared information on CCI pre-acceleration phase and defined a work plan to respect the project timeline.

Subtasks CC1.2.3 and **CC1.2.4** have been developed by other Spokes and will not be treated hereon.

Methodology: The methodology to carry on **Subtask CC1.2.2** for Spoke 8 for the first cycle have been extensively reported in the previous annual report. As stated, the engagement of the proposers happened via these channels:

- 43 through the event organized by UniTS and PoloAA on November 11, 2023;
- 6 through the activity "Play with canvas" (Business Model Game Labs-Laboratori d'Innovazione) held at UniTS;
- via online promotion;
- were the winner of the 2023 hackathons described in the previous report;
- 10 through other activities of UniTS.

As for the second cycle, the following activities have been carried out:

1. Offline presentation of the call, namely during academic lectures, one-to-one meetings and the Contamination Lab seminars.

On July 19th, 2024, the call was presented to the students engaged in the UNITS Contamination Lab training.

On September 23rd, 2024 (the first day of academic lectures at UniTS) the call was presented to the students of the "Management of Innovation" course. This course is open to all students from all departments.

One-to-one meetings with potential researchers and administrative staff have been organized. Among the recruiting initiatives, the Spoke 8 performed a dedicated Hackathon for motivating young students to participate in the iNEST call for startups. It was called 'Blue Way Hackathon' and was held in Ancona on May 22nd and 23rd, 2024, during the "Tipicità in Blu" Festival, as part of the #BlueEconomy days.

2. Online (email and social media) promotion of the open call for early-stage startups and researchers (August-September 2024), thanks to a dedicated poster with a QR code linking to an internal Spoke 8 Google form where to present the problem addressed and the idea proposed.

On August 5th we sent an informational email to all the UniTS Departments' Dean, who were invited to forward the call to students, lecturers and administrative personnel or publish it on social media, Department websites or physically in the university buildings.

We sent emails to participants of the first iNEST call; the Ancona hackathon's participants and the contacts of the Contamination Lab mailing list.

Call for Ideas and Early Stage Start-ups

Bando per startup o spinoff di ricerca in fase iniziale con progetti / soluzioni in target con i macro temi del progetto

Call for Ideas - Cross Cutting Activity 1. Sostegno alla generazione e allo sviluppo di start-up e spin-off

Come partecipare? Basta avere un'idea innovativa e d'impatto, anche a grandi linee. Non è necessario avere un progetto preciso: ti aiuteremo a svilupparlo!

Macro temi del progetto

- Smart industries
- Smart agri-food and nutrition
- Health tech and services
- Smart and sustainable living
- Creative Industries
- Tourism
- Technologies and services for natural ecosystems

Le idee che passeranno le fasi di selezione accederanno nel 2025 a un programma di Accelerazione di 5 mesi, che porterà le startup a validare il mercato e a un modello di business scalabile. Le candidature sono ammesse entro il 28 settembre 2024.

Per maggiori informazioni:

Sito web
www.consorzioinest.it

Mail
euprojects@poloaa.it

Per inviare la candidatura inquadra il QR Code e compila il Google Form

The second cycle saw the opening of the online call for proposals at the end of June. After the ending of the 'hunting' stage (8th September, 2024), the call closed on September 28th, 2024.

In the second cycle, the Spoke 8's scouting activity was more focused on research-oriented and high-level initiatives, as well as on the channeling the startups of the first cycle that still wanted to participate in iNEST: Lite AI, Slam Tech Nutrition and Bioxgen. All the applications for the Calls for Ideas and Early Stage Start-ups were collected in a common database.

Start-up and research projects of the first and second call were selected according to the Pre-acceleration path through the following steps:

1. **Pre-screening**, performed by the Scouting Specialists. During the first cycle, among the 65 proposals collected, 27 were pre-screened as interesting, but all 65 received a tailor-made feedback focusing on these aspects:
 - Technical feasibility
 - Economic feasibility
 - Areas to focus on
 - Areas to improve

They also received provision of iNEST training resources and additional training proposal from SPOKE 8 (through the Contamination Lab of UniTS).

They were invited to continue the application process through the submission of more detailed selection form and pitch deck, with deadline 01.03.2024.

In the second cycle, Spoke 8 received 24 proposals and pre-screened 11 proposals. Also in this case, a personalized feedback has been sent to all the proposals, with invitation to submit a full proposal with selection form and pitch-deck by 21/10/2024.

2. **Screening**. It was performed by Scouting Specialists of PoloAA and UniTS, supported by Mariangela Scorrano and Chiara Marinelli, who served as a startup coach during the first Pre-Acceleration cycle of activities.

In the first cycle, the scouting specialists selected 5 startups for the Committee screening. In the second cycle, the scouting specialists selected 5 startups for the Committee screening. The 5 startups had different focuses: Smart Industries (1), Smart and Sustainable Living (1), Technologies and Services for Natural Ecosystems (1), Health Tech and Services (1) and Smart Agri-food and Nutrition (1).
3. **Committee evaluation**. It was performed in 2024 by the CC1 Committee in March (for 1st cycle) and in October (for 2nd cycle). In the first cycle, 100% of the 5 ideas presented by Spoke 8 to the Committee on 12/03/2024 were accepted for the Selection Day in Venice on March 19th, 2024. As for the second cycle, two startups from Spoke 8 were chosen for the Selection day in Udine: OPTILINK and Sipeom.
4. **Selection Day**. During the Selection Day, all start-up projects from all Spokes that passed the Committee evaluation were presented to the CC1 Committee (and an external jury, in the case of the 2nd cycle). The Committee then selected about 15 teams for the Acceleration phase. The Selection Day of the 1st cycle was held at the IUAV University of Venice on March 19, 2024. Two startups from Spoke 8 were selected for the Acceleration programme: NEMO AI and Knowgen Labs. The Selection Day of the 2nd cycle was held at the University of Udine on December 3, 2024. Both startups from Spoke 8 were selected for the Acceleration programme: OPTILINK and Sipeom.

Focus on Task CC1.3: Acceleration activities within Spoke 8

Background/State of the Art: Sub-task CC1.3.1 and Sub-task CC1.3.2 have been developed by other Spokes and will not be treated hereon.

For what concerns **Sub-task CC1.3.3**, a centralized Acceleration program has been developed for the founders of the selected teams so that they can acquire all the knowledge and skills to build a solid business model. With a holistic approach to innovation that leverages synergies between academic research and the business world, the iNEST Accelerator aims to foster the creation of high-tech start-ups, generate skilled employment, and promote sustainable economic development in Northeastern Italy. Particular emphasis is placed on the preparation of a pitch, as each Acceleration cycle is closed by the Demo Day, a public event where start-up projects are presented to potential investors and professionals, offering significant networking opportunities and potential business collaborations. Start-up projects are evaluated by an external jury, and the most deserving teams are given an award.

Methodology: For **Sub-task CC1.3.3**, the Acceleration program has been structured with a series of in-person workshops, held by professionals involved in Cross-Cutting Activity 1 across the whole Triveneto region, which blend theory and practice in innovation and entrepreneurship. Pitch clinics, in which teams have the opportunity to try their pitch in front of a jury (either internal or external), are also part of the program. In the following, each of the two programs is detailed.

- 1st cycle:
 - Workshop #1: April 19–20, 2024, in Trieste (UniTS): “Strategy innovation and problem-client fit”.
 - Workshop #2: May 10–11, 2024, in Padua: “Solution and market fit”.
 - Workshop #3: May 31–June 1, 2024, in Trento: “Profit model” and a pitch session test.
 - Workshop #4: June 28–29, 2024, in Trieste (SISSA): “Go to market strategy”.
 - Workshop #5: August 30–31, 2024, in Verona: “Funding strategy”.
 - Pitch Clinic: September 20, 2024, in Venice.

The plenary meeting frequency of the SS team has coincided with the dates and locations of the program workshops. Spoke 8 participated either in person or online to the meetings of the programme.

- 2nd cycle:
 - Workshop #1: January 17–18, 2025, in Trento: “Introduction and presentation of the strategic plan”.
 - Workshop #2: February 7–8, 2025, in Verona: “Problem, current solutions, and proposition”.
 - Workshop #3: February 28–March 1, 2025, in Udine: “Market and competition”.
 - Workshop #4: March 14–15, 2025, in Venice (Ca’ Foscari): “Governance, vision, mission, and strategy; Business Model”.
 - Pitch Clinic #1: April 4, 2025, in Venice (IUAV).
 - Workshop #5: May 9–10, 2025, in Bolzano: “Action plan & eco-fin plan”.
 - Workshop #6: May 23–24, 2025, in Trieste: “Eco-fin plan & funding”.
 - Pitch Clinic #2: June 6, 2025, in Verona.

Workshops are based on the lean startup methodology, which enables teams to test and adjust their hypotheses about solutions and markets quickly. This approach is particularly effective for technologies

emerging from research, which require a clear and flexible commercialization path. Another essential component of the program is peer learning—participants learn from one another by sharing experiences, challenges, and solutions, accelerating their start-up's development. Every start-up team is assigned two coaches, professionals from affiliated universities and institutions who help them apply what learned in workshops to their specific start-up contexts. Coaches follow start-up teams during the workshops and can also organize one-on-one coaching sessions. The 1st cycle of the program also included five webinars, held by mentors—professionals from specific sectors who help all teams in a single field:

- Webinar #1: Presentation of psychological profiles (June 19, 2024) by Beniamino Mirisola;
- Webinar #2: Marketing, customer acquisition, sales (June 24, 2024) by Giacomo Tesolin;
- Webinar #3: IP strategy (July 5, 2024) by Elisa Toniolo;
- Webinar #4: Establishment of an innovative S.r.l. between civil and tax regulations (September 13, 2024) by Valter Carturo;
- Webinar #5: Innovative start-ups and contractual frameworks (September 27, 2024) by Paolo Guaragnella and Giorgio Abbadessa.

The 1st cycle of the activity was concluded by a Demo Day, held in Verona on October 25, 2024. A jury of 7 investors was featured: Augusto Coppola from Cloud Accelerator, Alvisè Bonivento from Indaco Venture Partners Sgr, Arianna Tibuzzi from Obloo Ventures, Michele Marcaccio from FNDX to represent Gellify, Tommaso Maschera from Plug and Play, Alessandro Nitti from CIV (Compagnia per l'Innovazione e i Valori), and Enrico Fili from CDP Venture Capital SGR.

None of the UniTS startups was awarded and entered the Fundraising stage.

Ongoing activities: As for **Sub-task CC1.3.3**, the 2nd cycle of the Acceleration program is about to begin. All appointments, apart from the Demo Day, have been scheduled. The AcceleratorApp software is being used for the organization and management of this cycle of the activity.

Focus on Task CC1.4: Fundraising

As for **CC1.4 Fundraising activities**, Spoke 8 has prepared a detailed plan of action, which is detailed as follows. It will be addressed to startups participating in the acceleration programme of both the first and the second cycle.

Background/state of the art: since June 2024, the representatives of Spoke 8 from UniTS and PoloAA started to plan the Fundraising initiatives scheduled for 2025. They agreed on the organisation of a composite program to be held in different stages and covering full-fledged topics on financial aspects concerning the startup funding. The fundraising phase aims at leading successful start-ups to become scaleups. The Spoke 8, in this phase, will support investment-ready scaleups to fulfil their financial needs, by developing a fundraising network, identifying and approaching potential investors including VC/BA and helping in negotiating/structuring investment deals.

Methodology: The start-ups emerging from the iNEST acceleration program will be supported by specialists and guided towards adopting the most effective approaches to fundraising. Spoke 8 will organize the following training cycles, involving consultants and participants from the acceleration programs of both the first and second cycles:

- The Vocabulary of Credit: This training will focus on the terminology and processes required to access credit, crowdfunding, and investor relations, providing participants with the essential foundations to navigate the financial landscape confidently.
- Meetings with Banks: These sessions will explore avenues for cooperation between entrepreneurs and key stakeholders, examine best practices for financial guarantees, and work on developing innovative financial products tailored to the needs of young entrepreneurs and start-ups.
- Meetings with Enterprises: Start-ups will have the opportunity to present their ideas through structured "speed-dating" activities, fostering direct interaction with potential industry partners.
- Consultations with a Venture Capitalist: These sessions will help participants:
 - understand market dynamics and the role of venture capitalists in driving the success of innovative start-ups;
 - refine their business plans through a dedicated platform, enhancing their ability to secure international funding.
- Specialized Start-Up Support Services: A specialized firm will offer targeted services to evaluate business potential, identify effective business models, and support capital-raising efforts by connecting start-ups with investors and assisting in pre-money valuations.

Synergistic actions among the various consultants involved will enable a thorough evaluation of each project's maturity level and pre-money stage. This approach will assist start-ups in identifying the most suitable financial instruments or types of investors based on their project characteristics and provide guidance during the initial phases of engagement with potential investors.

Ongoing activities: The Spoke 8 members are currently involved in the call for experts to be invited to the meetings and who will hold the information sessions. In addition, they are organizing the events around the Triveneto and the final event of the fundraising cycle.

8.3. SPOKE 8 CCI DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES

The dissemination activities carried out by the Spoke 8 POLOAA and UniTS for iNEST CCI sometimes overlap with the initiatives described in section 2.2. Adding to the informative material presented above, on June 11th, 2024 UniTS also organised a hands-on laboratory 'Business Model Game Lab – Laboratori d'Innovazione' for the students of the Department of Life Sciences (in the course taught by prof. Lucia Gardossi). The workshop was organized in the context of a two-day seminar entitled "Biotecnologie per la chimica sostenibile: innovazione e trasferimento tecnologico" and was held at the Department of Economics, Management, Mathematics and Statistical Sciences (DEAMS). Here, heterogeneous groups of students were invited to play with the business model canvas to craft new business ideas.

Martedì 11 giugno	
9.00-13.00	
<i>Workshop:</i> 'Business Model Game Labs-laboratori d'innovazione'	
<p>Workshop coordinato dal professor Guido Bortoluzzi, ordinario di Management dell'innovazione e Imprenditorialità presso il Dipartimento di Scienze Economiche, Aziendali, Matematiche e Statistiche (DEAMS) dell'Università di Trieste e della MIB School of Management, con la collaborazione della studentessa di dottorato in Circular Economy del DEAMS Chiara Marinelli.</p> <p>L'evento si terrà nell'ambito del progetto iNEST, finanziato dal PNRR-NextGenerationEU e che include 9 università italiane del Nord-Est e mira a promuovere l'innovazione e l'imprenditorialità.</p> <p>Il laboratorio interattivo fornirà ai partecipanti un'infarinatura sul business model canvas e li coinvolgerà direttamente nell'analisi di un modello di business aziendale esistente, con l'obiettivo di fornire loro le nozioni di base di imprenditorialità e stimolarli al pensiero imprenditoriale in modo collaborativo e coinvolgente.</p>	

In addition, some students recruited through UniTS-POLOAA performed a dedicated Hackathon for motivating young students to participate in the iNEST call for startups. The 'Blue Way Hackathon' held in Ancona on May 22nd and 23rd, 2024, during the "Tipicità in Blu" Festival, had the goal to recruit participants for the second iNEST Call for ideas and promote the development of solutions in the blue economy sector. "The sea of the future is sustainable, green, and respectful of biodiversity" was the claim: 43 young students had 14 hours of preparatory study with the Starter Kit and 36 hours in person to propose innovative solutions to marine problems. The challenge given to the participants consisted in the development of a service or product in the Blue Economy sector using digital technologies according to the principles of ecological and social sustainability. There were 20 mentors available, including professors, company directors, R&D managers, researchers, visual designers, and marketing and business strategy experts. They had only two minutes to convince the jury that their idea is feasible and innovative. Here the videos of the event:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LnubZd1h3u8&list=PLJ9xn0eU5enXkwC6EZ6ISbo6TWsoelF2w>

8.4. SPOKE 8 CCI MAIN RESULTS

First and foremost, the diverse range of CCI activities conducted within the framework of Spoke 8 has equipped participants with valuable tools to better develop and present their entrepreneurial ideas. The direct involvement of students and researchers from different departments and backgrounds yielded substantial positive impacts on their education in entrepreneurship and innovation, enhancing their practical application of business concepts. These interactive learning activities have not only

improved participants' grasp of real-world case studies but also deepened their understanding of business concepts and expanded their knowledge of key topics related to entrepreneurial culture, technological advancement and territorial growth.

Second, the initiatives facilitated the engagement of a broader audience, resulting in the collection of over 60 innovative ideas on diverse topics for the first cycle call and more than 20 for the second round. A value added of these numbers stands in the variety of expertise and level of maturity of participants, ranging from expert researchers to students with diverse educational backgrounds. During the first Acceleration cycle, this promoted cross-fertilisation and cooperation among the startup team members. During the second one, hopefully the same will occur.

Third, the initiatives of Spoke 8 CCI contributed to the involvement and on-the-field training of two UniTS PhD students, Lorenzo La Porta and Chiara Marinelli, acting as startup coaches during the first Acceleration training. In this context, a relevant success of the first cycle of the Acceleration cycle consisted in the training and development of two UniTS-PoloAA startups during the entire program. Although they were not awarded during the final Pitch Day of the first cycle in Verona, they are currently engaged in other activities for business development and are still working to improve and implement their innovation ideas.

Last, the necessity to create interdisciplinary educational materials and maximize the innovation potential of the collected entrepreneurial ideas strengthened collaboration among the various stakeholders involved. This reinforcement of cooperation between diverse key actors has significantly contributed to carry out the iNEST initiatives and promote close collaboration among those involved.

8.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN

During the implementation of the activities under CCI, some challenges were encountered.

The first Call for Ideas attracted a significant number of participants, as the goal was to engage a broad audience and raise awareness about the key concepts of innovation and entrepreneurship. Consequently, the selection phase required substantial effort. In the second cycle, however, a different strategy was adopted to ensure that only high-quality ideas with genuine funding potential applied for the Call for Start-ups. All the pre-selected ideas were deemed worthy. Furthermore, to enhance the transparency of the evaluation process, the Committee organized a jury for the selection day, comprising both committee members and external experts.

From September, 1st, 2024, with the handover from prof. Guido Bortoluzzi, the internal coordination within UNITS departments passed to Prof. Mariangela Scorrano. This transition introduced some adjustments to roles and workflows within UNITS. Regular internal meetings were introduced to foster clearer communication among team members and university stakeholders, ensuring a shared understanding of objectives and progress. A structured timeline was developed to ensure that dissemination activities and events were strategically planned and coordinated, optimizing their impact and reach. Feedback from team members and university stakeholders have been actively sought and incorporated into ongoing activities (to fine-tune approaches and improve outcomes). Apart from what previously described above, the overall proxy responsibility and coordination for the all spoke 8 continues to stay within POLOAA.

Agreed with the CCI Committee, great effort has been devoted to better focus the fundraising stage on consultancy, with the involvement of experts able to support investment-ready scaleups to fulfil their financial needs. This required a reorganization of the activities and a budget shift whose approval, however, registered some delay. In the end the Spoke 8 CCI budget was successfully updated and all the planned activities are going to start.

These corrective actions have already contributed to more cohesive operations and better alignment of CCI activities with the overall goals of the iNEST project. Moving forward, these measures will continue to support effective implementation and enhance collaboration within the consortium.

8.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES

For the 2nd cycle of Acceleration of CCI, the main challenge will be to improve the program and replicate the successful stages of the 1st cycle. In addition, a key challenge will consist in the planning of the meetings for the Fundraising sessions and the recruitment of experts to be involved. The recruitment of the Company for the last training stage of the Fundraising cycle will also be one of the main challenges, along with the invitation of the VCs and the BAs for the final event. This will be the core of the future activities for this first semester of 2025 for the Spoke 8 CCI team.

9. SPOKE 9 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the Cross-Cutting Activity 1

The research activities of Spoke 9 address current issues in the sectors of mathematical and numerical models, scientific computing, and digital twins. These are supported and enhanced by four Research Topics (RTs), namely:

- **RT1 - Mathematical, Numerical and Data-driven Modeling**, which aims to create a framework for the mathematical modeling of complex systems, i.e. a mathematical description of systems composed of many interacting parts;
- **RT2 - Model Order Reduction**, an advanced numerical approach that is employed to reduce the computational cost of numerical simulations;
- **RT3 - Automatic Learning for Digital Twins**, devoted to the application of automatic learning techniques, such as machine learning and reduced order models, in a high-performance computing setting;
- **RT4 - Applications of DT in Industry, Medicine, Environmental Sciences, Daily life**, whose goal is to review the most updated techniques regarding the applications of digital twins to the environment, daily life, and infrastructures.

In this scientific context, **Cross-Cutting Activity 1** plays an important role in fostering a coordinated and transversal approach across all Spokes within the iNEST project. Aligned with the framework of an innovation ecosystem, this activity serves the purpose of valorizing innovative ideas arising from the research activities of Spoke 9 and facilitating the generation and development of research start-ups and spin-offs.

9.1. SPOKE 9 CC1 OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW

Within the iNEST Consortium, the overall goal of Cross-Cutting Activity 1 is to promote the generation and the selection of innovative ideas emerging from the scientific activities of Spoke 9 and to transform them into research start-ups and spin-offs. To this aim, CC1 is subdivided into four distinct phases.

The first phase of CC1 concerns the planning and the validation of all activities. This involved hiring dedicated personnel to support the activities as planned by the committee of the CC1.

Currently, the 1st cycle of CC1 is coming to an end, as the **Fundraising** phase is occurring. Two start-up projects originally selected through the 1st Spoke 9 Call for Start-up Pre-seed—**SINDREL** and **Sniff-nano**, both from SISSA—have reached this phase; the current objective is to help their team to contact Venture Capitalists and Business Angels who could support the further growth of these projects and their establishment as business realities. In this final phase, the management of the fundraising network is essential to collect all the possible funding possibilities and the partnership solutions. The founders will be supported with events and networking occasions with the aim of collecting financial resources and developing their business ideas.

Meanwhile, the 2nd cycle of CC1 has officially commenced. In particular, the Pre-acceleration phase of this cycle has just concluded. The 2nd **Selection Day** of CC1 took place on December 3 in Udine. In light

of what was showcased during the Selection Day, the CCI Committee has admitted three start-up projects related to Spoke 9, originally selected through the 2nd Spoke 9 Call for Start-up Pre-seed, to the Acceleration phase: **BIOXGEN** (from SISSA), **COCAL** (from OGS), and **Easy Resp** (from SISSA). The goal of this next phase is to help these teams in developing a solid business model; their founders will attend the new Acceleration program, consisting of 6 workshops and 2 pitch clinics designed to hone their entrepreneurial skills and prepare them for the challenges of scaling their ventures. In parallel, efforts in public communication will ensure that all program milestones will be highlighted. Special focus will be placed on the mission, vision, and innovative aspects of the start-up projects through the production of dedicated content, such as YouTube videos, to showcase their journey and achievements to a broader audience.

9.2. SPOKE 9 CCI TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES

List of CCI Tasks:

- CCI.1: Planning and validation
- **CCI.2: Pre-acceleration**
 - Sub Task CCI.2.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (10 Scouting specialists, one for each spoke - two for spoke 5, and pre-acceleration officer) of the pre-acceleration phase.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 9-40
 - Sub Task CCI.2.2: Implementation of the Scouting Stage to attract entrepreneurs-to-be from the university's ecosystems and drive the research effort toward a proof-of-concept.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 10-23
 - Sub Task CCI.2.3: Implementation of the online Entrepreneurial training through Management & Educational Platform to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 12-26
 - Sub Task CCI.2.4: Open innovation activities. The objective of this task is to establish relationships with companies and other partners in order to facilitate the development of new projects, spinoffs, and co-innovation activities between universities, startups, and companies.
Responsible: UNIUD
Duration: months 9-40

- CC1.3: Acceleration
 - Sub Task CC1.3.1: Development of the Key Standardized Elements (Acceleration Framework; Acceleration Physical Spaces) of the acceleration phase to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
Responsible: UNIVR
Duration: months 11-34
 - Sub Task CC1.3.2: Engagement and coordination of the Key Actors (Acceleration officer, 2 StartUp Analysts) of the acceleration phase.
Responsible: UNIVR
Duration: months 14-40
 - Sub Task CC1.3.3: Implementation of the Acceleration phase through Pitch Building & Pitch Session, Selection day, Onboarding and SCUM program. the objective of this phase is to bring the start-ups to validate the market and a scalable business model.
Responsible: UNIVR
Duration: months 15-32
- CC1.4: Fundraising

Focus on Task CC1.2: Scouting and Pre-acceleration activities within Spoke 9

Background/State of the Art: For Task CC1.2, the SISSA Valorisation and Innovation Office supports Spoke 9 activities. Technology and knowledge transfer are considered crucial and strategic activities, and concrete and structured actions are taken systemically to promote innovation, valorize internal research and talents, and improve the impact of the research results on society and the productive and economic ecosystem. For what concerns **Sub-task CC1.2.1**, the following figures followed Spoke 9 initiatives within CC1:

- Alberto Cavazza, who covered the role of Scouting Specialist for Spoke 9;
- Luca Mingotti Landriani, who covered the role of Event Communication Specialist (still holding the position);
- Sara Anzuinelli, who covered the role of Event Communication Assistant.

At the end of the 1st cycle of CC1, the Scouting Specialist and the Event Communication Assistant embarked on new professional and educational paths, making it necessary to replace these two roles. The replacements have been identified, and the selection process was completed on January 7, 2025. The new hires will begin their roles at Spoke 9 by the end of January.

As for **Sub-task CC1.2.2**, the implementation of the Scouting Stage has consisted of preparing a Call for Start-up Pre-seed, one for each Spoke and each cycle of the activity. For Spoke 9, two Calls for Start-up Pre-seed were prepared by the Scouting Specialist, under the supervision of the Scouting Officer and the Assistant Scouting Officers:

- The 1st Call for Start-up Pre-seed was opened in December 2023 and closed in February 2024;
- The 2nd Call for Start-up Pre-seed was opened in June 2024 and closed in September 2024.

Sub-task CC1.2.3 has been developed by other Spokes and will not be treated hereon. As for **Sub-task CC1.2.4**, a list of 66 innovative companies from Northeastern Italy has been prepared by the Open Innovation Manager. An Open Innovation Day is scheduled on January 30, 2025, in Padua; the iNEST project will be presented and a symbolic prize will be given to the 66 companies.

Methodology: For what concerns **Sub-task CC1.2.2**, all the applications for the two Calls for Start-up Pre-seed were collected in a common database. Potential start-uppers were contacted by the Scouting Specialist to organize a series of one-to-one meetings to explore together the potential of innovative ideas and research results to valorize. In this phase, the contribution of the Valorisation and Innovation Office of SISSA has been recognized as fundamental, in particular to guide the Scouting Specialist to attract internal doctoral students and researchers potentially interested in proposing their ideas. Start-up projects were then selected according to the Pre-acceleration funnel, which was designed by the Scouting Officer and his Assistants. The Pre-acceleration funnel consists of the following steps:

1. **Pre-screening.** It is performed by Scouting Specialists.
2. **Screening.** It is performed by Scouting Specialists.
3. **Committee evaluation.** It is performed by the CC1 Committee.
4. **Selection Day.** During the Selection Day, all start-up projects from all Spokes that passed the Committee evaluation are presented to the CC1 Committee (and a possible external jury, in the case of the 2nd cycle). The Committee then selects about 10–15 teams for the Acceleration phase. The Selection Day of the 1st cycle was held at the Iuav University of Venice on March 19, 2024. The Selection Day of the 2nd cycle was held at the University of Udine on December 3, 2024.

For **Sub-task CC1.2.4**, the 66 companies were selected by the Open Innovation Manager through a set of innovation performance indicators based on financial data, the number of patents held by the companies, and data on R&D and innovation projects funded through public calls. Companies with a turnover exceeding €50 million were considered.

Ongoing activities: As for **Sub-task CC1.2.2**, all activities described before are now over. For what concerns **Sub-task CC1.2.4**, the Open Innovation Day is currently being organized. The role of Spoke 9 will be to promote it among potentially interested companies, to favor networking and foster the expansion of the Northeastern innovation ecosystem.

Focus on Task CC1.3: Acceleration activities within Spoke 9

Background/State of the Art: Sub-task CC1.3.1 and Sub-task CC1.3.2 have been developed by other Spokes and will not be treated hereon.

For what concerns **Sub-task CC1.3.3**, a centralized Acceleration program has been developed for the founders of the selected teams so that they can acquire all the knowledge and skills to build a solid business model. With a holistic approach to innovation that leverages synergies between academic research and the business world, the iNEST Accelerator aims to foster the creation of high-tech start-ups, generate skilled employment, and promote sustainable economic development in Northeastern Italy. Particular emphasis is placed on the preparation of a pitch, as each Acceleration cycle is closed by the Demo Day, a public event where start-up projects are presented to potential investors and professionals, offering significant networking opportunities and potential business collaborations. Start-up projects are evaluated by an external jury, and the most deserving teams are given an award.

Methodology: For **Sub-task CCI.3.3**, the Acceleration program has been structured with a series of in-person workshops, held by professionals involved in Cross-Cutting Activity 1 across the whole Triveneto region, which blend theory and practice in innovation and entrepreneurship. Pitch clinics, in which teams have the opportunity to try their pitch in front of a jury (either internal or external), are also part of the program. In the following, each of the two programs is detailed.

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 - Workshop #4: June 28–29, 2024, in Trieste (SISSA): “Go to market strategy”.
 - Workshop #5: August 30–31, 2024, in Verona: “Funding strategy”.
 - Pitch Clinic: September 20, 2024, in Venice.
- 2nd cycle:
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 - Workshop #4: March 14–15, 2025, in Venice (Ca’ Foscari): “Governance, vision, mission, and strategy; Business Model”.
 - Pitch Clinic #1: April 4, 2025, in Venice (luav).
 - Workshop #5: May 9–10, 2025, in Bolzano: “Action plan & eco-fin plan”.
 - Workshop #6: May 23–24, 2025, in Trieste: “Eco-fin plan & funding”.
 - Pitch Clinic #2: June 6, 2025, in Verona.

Workshops are based on the lean startup methodology, which enables teams to test and adjust their hypotheses about solutions and markets quickly. This approach is particularly effective for technologies emerging from research, which require a clear and flexible commercialization path. Another essential component of the program is peer learning—participants learn from one another by sharing experiences, challenges, and solutions, accelerating their start-up's development. Every start-up team is assigned two coaches, professionals from affiliated universities and institutions who help them apply what learned in workshops to their specific start-up contexts. Coaches follow start-up teams during the workshops and can also organize one-on-one coaching sessions. The 1st cycle of the program also included five webinars, held by mentors—professionals from specific sectors who help all teams in a single field:

- Webinar #1: Presentation of psychological profiles (June 19, 2024) by Beniamino Mirisola;
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- Webinar #3: IP strategy (July 5, 2024) by Elisa Toniolo;
- Webinar #4: Establishment of an innovative S.r.l. between civil and tax regulations (September 13, 2024) by Valter Carturo;
- Webinar #5: Innovative start-ups and contractual frameworks (September 27, 2024) by Paolo Guaragnella and Giorgio Abbadessa.

The 1st cycle of the activity was concluded by a Demo Day, held in Verona on October 25, 2024. A jury of 7 investors was featured: Augusto Coppola from Cloud Accelerator, Alvisè Bonivento from Indaco Venture Partners Sgr, Arianna Tibuzzi from Obloo Ventures, Michele Marcaccio from FNDX to represent Gellify, Tommaso Maschera from Plug and Play, Alessandro Nitti from CIV (Compagnia per l'Innovazione e i Valori), and Enrico Fili from CDP Venture Capital SGR.

Ongoing activities: As for **Sub-task CC1.3.3**, the 2nd cycle of the Acceleration program is about to begin. All appointments, apart from the Demo Day, have been scheduled. The AcceleratorApp software is being used for the organization and management of this cycle of the activity.

9.3. SPOKE 9 CC1 DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES

Focus on Task CC1.2: Scouting and Pre-acceleration activities within Spoke 9

For what concerns **Sub-task CC1.2.2**, to promote the application to the two Spoke 9 Calls for Start-up Pre-seed among doctoral students and researchers, two events have been organized at SISSA:

- iNEST Meet&Drink, held on January 17, 2024;
- iNEST: Ideas for Innovation, held on July 9, 2024.

During these events, iNEST and Cross-Cutting Activity 1 were presented by Spoke 9 and CC1 representatives, and guidelines for preparing a good pitch were provided. For iNEST Meet&Drink, two SISSA start-up CEOs (Andrea Martini from FAST Computing and Enrico Siagri from MATERYS) were involved, so that they could provide insight into the entrepreneurial world to the aspiring innovators. For iNEST: Ideas for Innovation, instead, two Spoke 9 start-up co-founders involved in the 1st cycle of the program were involved, so that they could share their experience within the program and provide tips.

The opening of the two Calls and the promotion of these two events were disseminated through news articles (on the iNEST, Spoke 9, and SISSA websites), social media posts (SISSA LinkedIn and Facebook webpages), e-mails by the SISSA Valorisation and Innovation Office, and messages on students' internal chat groups. All these activities have been carried out with the help and the coordination of SISSA Press Office and SISSA Valorisation and Innovation Office.

The two Selection Days were also publicly disseminated, through articles on the iNEST and Spoke 9 websites, and posts on the iNEST social media pages (LinkedIn and Facebook). The first Selection Day was also promoted with a YouTube video and two press releases (before and after the event), which were prepared with the aid of both the Ca' Foscari University and the Luav University of Venice Press Offices.

Finally, this phase of the activity has been described on the [iNEST](#) and [Spoke 9](#) websites, and the results of the 1st cycle were presented in a [dedicated webpage](#) and social media post.

For **Sub-task CC1.2.4**, promotional materials for the Open Innovation Day are currently being prepared, in order to increase participation, as well as a press release that will be sent to local media in the whole Triveneto area, with the help of the Press Offices of all universities involved in iNEST.

Focus on Task CC1.3: Acceleration activities within Spoke 9

For what concerns **Sub-task CC1.3.3**, the 1st cycle of the Acceleration program has been publicly disseminated with a news article on the iNEST website, a social media post on the iNEST accounts recapping every workshop, and YouTube videos of each start-up project involved in the program. A social media post was also prepared to promote the five webinars, and a dedicated section has been

prepared on the [CCI page](#) of the iNEST website.

The Demo Day has been promoted with a dedicated landing page on Eventbrite, a series of news articles on the iNEST website, and a number of social media posts on the iNEST accounts. Press releases, both for local newspapers and for online websites focusing on start-ups and innovation, have been published. The local press release has been prepared and disseminated with the aid of Press Offices from all universities involved in iNEST, particularly the University of Verona, whose members also conducted a video interview with relevant figures and start-ups. A number of articles concerning the start-up projects presented in the 1st Demo Day have been featured in local newspapers. Furthermore, all the key information concerning the start-up projects has been inserted in a dedicated booklet and in a [page on the iNEST website](#).

9.4. SPOKE 9 CCI MAIN RESULTS

For what concerns **Sub-task CC1.2.2**, **10** applications were registered in the 1st Spoke 9 Call for Start-up Pre-seed, and **5** applications were registered in the 2nd Spoke 9 Call for Start-up Pre-seed. These numbers were achieved both with the coordinated action of the Scouting Specialist and the SISSA Valorisation and Innovation Office, and with the two promotional events held at SISSA; in particular, 13 potential candidates were registered in iNEST Meet&Drink, whereas 12 potential candidates were registered in iNEST: Ideas for Innovation.

Following the Pre-acceleration funnel, ideas were then selected:

1. **Pre-screening.** In the 1st cycle, out of 10 applications for the Spoke 9 Call for Start-up Pre-seed, **5** ideas were admitted to the next selection step.
In the 2nd cycle, out of 11 applications, **6** ideas were admitted to the next selection step.
2. **Screening.** In the 1st cycle, out of 5 ideas from Spoke 9, **4** projects were admitted to the next selection step.
In the 2nd cycle, out of 6 ideas from Spoke 9, **5** projects were admitted to the next selection step.
3. **Committee evaluation.**
In the 1st cycle, out of 4 projects from Spoke 9, **4** were admitted to the next selection step.
In the 2nd cycle, out of 5 projects from Spoke 9, **4** were admitted to the next selection step.
4. **Selection Day.** Out of 4 projects from Spoke 9, **2** have been admitted to the 1st Acceleration program, joining 13 teams from other Spokes.
Out of 4 projects from Spoke 9, **3** have been admitted to the 2nd Acceleration program, joining 13 teams from other Spokes.

As for **Sub-task CC1.3.3**, 15 start-up teams have participated in the 1st cycle of the program, and 11 have presented their pitch during the Demo Day, including both teams from Spoke 9. SINDREL was awarded as the best start-up project of the program, whereas Sniff-nano was awarded as the second-best start-up project of the program. For the 2nd cycle of the program, 3 Spoke 9 teams will be present: BIOXGEN, COCAL, and Easy Resp.

9.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN

As for **Task CC1.2**, the main issue was the engagement of SISSA doctoral students and researchers, who are typically focused on basic research and pursue an academic path, being unaware of the possibilities of the entrepreneurial world. The two SISSA events helped to increase the number of applications, and

another solution for the 2nd cycle was to scout ideas among researchers from the other Spoke 9 Affiliates. In this regard, the coordination with the Valorisation and Innovation Office of SISSA has also played an important role. By working together on procedures and methodologies, including the organization of the two SISSA events, it was possible to start a synergistic activity between the Valorisation and Innovation Office and the Scouting Specialist, who reported to Tanja Lunardelli, the figure dedicated to internal scouting in SISSA, the continuation of the activities, the response of the people met, and the potential issues to be addressed regarding the protection and patenting of ideas.

For what concerns **Task CCI.3**, the main issue encountered with the development of the 1st Acceleration program was to integrate diverse innovation fields and support teams from varied technological sectors while respecting the different timelines required to validate markets. Moreover, the Selection Day and the pitch trials brought up that, in some cases, it was not clear why some projects needed investments and how they could be best supported. With the help of workshops and coaching sessions, all the teams, and in particular Spoke 9 teams, developed a solid business model and learned how to valorize their strengths in front of potential investors.

9.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES

With the beginning of the Fundraising phase, corresponding to **Task CCI.4**, the start-up projects of the 1st cycle are now meeting potential investors. On November 18, 2024, both Spoke 9 teams participated in a meeting with a Business Angel; on January 8, SINDREL was also involved in a meeting for the preparation of useful documentation and other tips. Valorizing these ideas and growing the business will be the main upcoming challenge for these start-up projects.

For the 2nd cycle of Cross-Cutting Activity 1, the main challenge will be to improve the Acceleration program and replicate what was successful in the 1st cycle. By establishing a new standard in acceleration and incubation programs, iNEST can become a reference for innovation among other incubators from Triveneto and Italy as a whole.

References

We report here the list of the links to the webpages relevant to Spoke 9 and in particular to Cross-Cutting Activity 1:

- [Spoke 9 website](#)
- [Cross-Cutting Activity 1 page on the iNEST website](#)
- [Cross-Cutting Activity 1 page on the Spoke 9 website](#)
- [Results of the 1st cycle of CCI \(page on the iNEST website\)](#)
- [List of news concerning CCI on the iNEST website](#)